

APPEL A PROJET FNSO « REEFTEMPS »

Fichier 1 : CV

CV 1 : Sylvie Fiat

CV 2 : Jérôme Aucan

CV 3 : Régis Hocdé

CV 4 : David Varillon

CV 5 : Céline Bachelier

CV 6 : Antoine De Ramon N'Yeurt

Sylvie Fiat

IRD, UMR ENTROPIE 250, Écologie Marine Tropicale des Océans Pacifique et Indien
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INGENIEUR DONNÉES ET INFORMATIQUE SCIENTIFIQUE

POSTE Ingénieur d'étude UMR ENTROPIE (Depuis 2015)

FORMATION Master Professionnel Informatique, Intégration de Systèmes Logiciels (2006), UFR des Sciences de Luminy, Université de la Méditerranée, Marseille, France

COMPÉTENCES

- Gestion de projets informatiques**
 - Développement Systèmes logiciels
 - Conception architecture logicielle orientée Open Source
 - Application des principes FAIR
 - Suivi AMOA
 - Expertise normes OGC (WMS, WFS, SOS, CSW)
- Gestion de données de la Recherche**
 - Rédaction de Data Management Plan (DMP)
 - Nettoyage et normalisation données et métadonnées
 - Open Data
 - Entrepôts de données
 - Référente Entrepôt DataSuds/IRD <http://datasuds.ird.fr/> pour ENTROPIE
- Gestion d'équipe**
 - Organisation du travail
 - Aide à la définition de planning
 - Suivi des demandes de travaux
- Plongée scientifique**
 - Classe 1B plongée hyperbare scientifique
 - Participation à de nombreuses campagnes en mer

PROJETS PRINCIPAUX REEFTEMPS (Depuis 2011) <http://reeftemps.science>
« Réseau d'observation des eaux côtières du Pacifique insulaire (ReefTEMPS) ». Porteur: Jérôme Aucan, UMR ENTROPIE. <http://doi.org/10.17882/55128>

Le projet ReefTEMPS mis en place par l'IRD en collaboration avec la Communauté du Pacifique (CPS) et l'University of South Pacific (SPC) a intégré récemment l'infrastructure de recherche ILICO.

Responsable technique évolution et maintenance du projet ReefTEMPS. Mise en œuvre des Sensor Observation Services (SOS) une norme de l'OGC interopérable et pérenne. Conception de l'architecture logicielle orientée Open Source. Application des principes FAIR. Mises aux normes des données diffusées en Open Source. Suivi des prestations. Mise à disposition des données via Seanoe et d'autres entrepôts de données.

ANR SEAMOUNTS (2019-2022) <http://seamounts.ird.nc>
« Seamounts as critical habitats for marine biodiversity » Porteur Laurent Vigliola, UMR ENTROPIE

SEAMOUNTS est un projet ANR qui étudie la biodiversité des monts sous marins par le biais de nouveaux outils tel que les Baited Remote Underwater Video System (BRUVS), l'ADN environnemental et le Deep Learning.

Porteur du Workpackage 6 *Database management*. Mise en place d'outils pour le partage et l'analyse de vidéos sous-marines sur les principes FAIR. Organisation de la valorisation des données dans des entrepôts.

LMI MIKAROKA (2020-2025) <http://mikaroka.ird.nc>

« Observation de la biodiversité marine côtière et de ses usages à Madagascar » Porteur Dominique Ponton, UMR ENTROPIE, Christian Ralijaona, IH.SM

Ce Laboratoire Mixte International (LMI) a pour objectif de mettre en place un observatoire de la biodiversité marine côtière et de ses usages à Madagascar, tout en accompagnant les partenaires dans le renforcement de leurs capacités de recherche et de formation.

Animateur de la composante Transversale : cette composante a pour objectif de mettre en œuvre une démarche afin de gérer de manière efficace les bases de données pour l'ensemble du LMI. Des outils seront ainsi développés ou adaptés, puis mis en œuvre afin que les données générées soient sauvegardées et pérennisées, et pour certaines, valorisées dans des bases de données internationales. Des formations seront proposées afin d'assurer une utilisation efficace des bases de données, le nettoyage et la normalisation des données.

LAGPLON (depuis 2009) <http://laqplon.ird.nc>

« Collection des données de biodiversité marine de l'Indo-Pacifique Sud ». Porteur: Claude Payri, UMR ENTROPIE <https://doi.org/10.15468/bifta5> <https://doi.org/10.15468/ymuzyz>

Lagplon est une base de données marines benthiques historique mise à jour au fil du temps notamment par les taxonomistes travaillant sur les groupes des macroalgues et des scléactiniaires. Publiées dans l'INPN, le GBIF et référencées par ECOSCOPE, les données sont mises à la disposition de la communauté internationale depuis 2012.

Porteur du projet informatique, gestion de la base de données, nettoyage et normalisation des données. Conception de l'architecture logicielle orientée Open Source. Application des principes FAIR. Mises aux normes des données diffusées en Open Source. 5 projets portés auprès du GBIF, de la FRB (2), de ECOSCOPE et de l'INPN. Diffusion des données dans les portails INPN et GBIF.

Publications / Conférences

Colloques, Congrès, Séminaires, Ateliers

Fiat Sylvie, ReefTEMPS, Network of coastal oceanic sensors, Open access data portal, RDA 15th Conference Melbourne 2020

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/reeftemps-network-coastal-oceanic-sensors-open-access-data-portal>.

Fiat Sylvie, Aucan Jérôme (2019), Comité utilisateurs OBLIC (Observatoire du Littoral de Nouvelle-Calédonie), Le Réseau ReefTEMPS, collecte et mise à disposition de données de température, vagues et niveau de la mer en Nouvelle-Calédonie et d'autres pays du Pacifique.

Fiat Sylvie, Hocdé, R., Critical Success Factors of the ReefTEMPS sensors-oriented environmental information system for a real operationality. Geospatial Sensing Conference, 2-4 September 2019 Munster, Germany.

Fiat, Sylvie, Aucan, J. (2018). Le réseau ReefTEMPS, réseau de capteurs de température, pression, salinité dans le domaine côtier du Pacifique Sud, Ouest et Sud-Ouest. Conférence GISDay 2018, Gouvernement de la Nouvelle-Calédonie.

Fiat Sylvie, Atelier Portage de services sous docker (3h). JDEV 2107, 4ème édition des Journées nationales du DEVeloppement logiciel, 4-7 juillet 2017, Marseille.

Fiat Sylvie, R. Hocdé. 2017. Groupe de travail ReefTEMPS est un réseau de capteurs de température, pression et salinité dans le domaine côtier du Pacifique Sud, Ouest et Sud-Ouest. JDEV 2107, 4ème édition des Journées nationales du DEVeloppement logiciel, 4-7 juillet 2017, Marseille.

Brissebrat G., Fiat Sylvie, Andriatiana A., Cheype Adrien, Grelet Jacques, Varillon David, Pelletier Bernard, Hocdé Régis. Sensor Observation System : optimisation d'un système d'information environnemental dédié capteurs : exemple du SI du réseau d'observation ReefTEMPS. Nantes : Renater, 2017, 9 p. JRES 2017 : Journées Réseaux de l'Enseignement et de la Recherche, Nantes (FRA), 2017/11/14-17.

Fiat Sylvie, Hocdé R. 2015. SI-TEC-PSO: retour d'expérience sur le système d'information dédié capteurs et reconstitution de séries temporelles de ReefTEMPS. Conférence: sist15 : Séries Interopérables et Systèmes de Traitement, 24-25 sept. 2015 Marseille, France.

Fiat Sylvie "Intérêt et organisation des métadonnées - exemple avec la collection des données de biodiversité marines de l'Indo-Pacifique - IRD de Nouméa". Atelier métadonnées ECOSCOPE 2014.

Fiat Sylvie, Hocdé R., "Collection des données de Biodiversité marine de l'Indo Pacifique - IRD Nouméa". Journée du GBIF 2013.

Articles

Dumas, P., Fiat, S., Durbano, A. et al. Citizen Science, a promising tool for detecting and monitoring outbreaks of the crown-of-thorns starfish *Acanthaster* spp.. *Sci Rep* 10, 291 (2020). DOI : 10.1038/s41598-019-57251-8

Payri Claude, Ramon N'yeurt A. de, Fiat Sylvie, Andréfouët Serge. Macroflore marine des Marquises. In : Galzin R. (ed.), Duron S.D. (ed.), Meyer J.Y. (ed.) Biodiversité terrestre et marine des îles Marquises, Polynésie française. Paris : Société Française d'Ichtyologie, 2016, p. 207-219. ISBN 2-9514628-9

Hocdé Régis, Fiat Sylvie. Le système d'information du "réseau de capteurs de température des eaux côtières dans la région du Pacifique Sud et Sud-Ouest". *Netcom*, 2013, 27 (2), p. 170-173. ISSN 2431-210X

Chapitres ou parties d'ouvrages

Fiat Sylvie, Payri C. 70 ans de données de biodiversité marine géoréférencées [encadré 18]. In : Payri Claude (ed.), Moatti Jean-Paul (pref.). Nouvelle-Calédonie : archipel de corail. Marseille (FRA) ; Nouméa : IRD ; Solaris, 2018, p. 143. ISBN 978-2-7099-2632-4

Vandel E., Fiat Sylvie, et al. L'inventaire de la biodiversité récifale pour le partage des connaissances. In : Payri Claude (ed.), Moatti Jean-Paul (pref.). Nouvelle-Calédonie: archipel de corail. Marseille (FRA) ; Nouméa : IRD ; Solaris, 2018, p. 141-144. ISBN 978-2-7099-2632-4

Dumas Pascal, Fiat Sylvie. Le programme Oreanet [encadré 21]. In : Payri Claude (ed.), Moatti Jean-Paul (pref.). Nouvelle-Calédonie : archipel de corail. Marseille (FRA) ; Nouméa : IRD ; Solaris, 2018, p. 177. ISBN 978-2-7099-2632-4

Jeux de données

Varillon David, Fiat Sylvie, Magron Franck, Allenbach Michel, Hoibian Thierry, De Ramon N'Yeurt Antoine, Ganachaud Alexandre, Aucan Jérôme, Pelletier Bernard, Hocdé Régis (2018). ReefTEMPS : the observation network of the coastal sea waters of the South, West and South-West Pacific. SEANOE. <http://doi.org/10.17882/55128>

N'Yeurt A et al. (2017). Collection des données de biodiversité marine de Nouvelle-Calédonie. Contacts : Fiat, S. UMR Entropie (IRD-UR-CNRS), Vandell, E. UMS PatriNat (AFB-CNRS-MNHN), Paris. Occurrence dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/bjfta5>.

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<https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=fr&user=Qg4A5hQAAAAJ>

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

2010-Present	<i>Research Scientist (CR1)</i>	Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD)
2009-2019	<i>Affiliate Graduate Faculty</i>	Oceanography Department, University of Hawai'i
2009-2010	<i>Assistant Research Scientist</i>	Bermuda Institute for Ocean Sciences (BIOS)
2005-2008	<i>Assistant Researcher</i>	University of Hawaii Sea Level Center (UHSLC/RCUH)
1999-2005	<i>Graduate Research Assistant</i>	Oceanography Department, University of Hawai'i

EDUCATION

Doctorate Degree, (Ph.D) <i>Physical Oceanography</i> Oceanography Department, University of Hawaii, Honolulu, Hawaii,	1999-2005
Postgraduate Diploma, (PGDip) <i>Applied Physics, Oceanography & Meteorology</i> Physics Department, James Cook University, Townsville, Australia	1997-1998
Engineering Diploma, (MS) <i>Marine Environment & Fluid mechanics</i> Ecole Nationale Supérieure de Techniques Avancées (ENSTA), Paris, France	1995-1998

CURRENT RESEARCH ACTIVITIES AND RESPONSABILITIES

- 2019-present : Co-Principal investigator (with Guillaume Dodet, Ifremer) : CFOSAT-COAST : Assessing the potential of CFOSAT mission for COASTal research. Funding by the French space agency (CNES).
- 2018-present : Head of the ReefTEMPs Pacific Island coastal ocean observation network (<http://reeftemps.science>), funded by IRD and CNRS, in collaboration with the Pacific Community (SPC) and University of South Pacific (USP).
- 2017-present : Principal investigator : Modeling of coastal tsunami hazards in New Caledonia. Funded by a grant from the New Caledonia Government.
- 2016-present : Co-Principal investigator : MANA (MANagement of Atolls) Observation and modeling of waves and currents in oyster-farming atolls in French Polynesia. Funded by a grant from the French research agency (ANR).
- 2016-present : Co-Principal investigator : EMIL (Morphological Evolution of Lagoon Islets). Funding with a research grant from the french ministry for overseas territory.
- 2015-present : Co-Principal investigator of COPRA project (Coastal Oceanography in the Pacific, Risk and Adaptation) : A joint research team between IRD and University of South Pacific (USP) in Suva, Fiji, funded by an international cooperation grant from IRD.
- 2012-present : Principal investigator : Observation and modeling of nearshore sea-level extremes in New Caledonia. Partly funded by a grant from CNRS.

PAST RESEARCH EXPERIENCE

2010-2014 : Co-Principal investigator : Creation of a multi-disciplinary time-series in the SouthWest Pacific (SPOT), based on ongoing repeat cruise surveys, and planned surface and subsurface moorings.

2010-2017 : Co-Principal investigator (with Fabrice Ardhuin, Ifremer) : Assessment of the characteristics of the global field of free surface infragravity waves in the context of a future satellite altimetry mission. Funding by the French space agency (CNES).

2009-2011 Co-Principal investigator Bermuda Atlantic Time-series Study (BATS) :

- Coupling between high-frequency physical processes and ecosystem response,
- Temporal variability of hydrographic properties and mixing from seasonal to decadal timescales.

1999 -2008 Co-PI : Pr Mark Merrifield, *University of Hawai'i, Department of Oceanography* :

- Mixing and turbulence created by internal waves along deep oceanic boundaries.
- Wave climatology, and wave-related extreme sea-level events.
- Maintenance and data processing for a network of 2 near-shore wave measuring buoys around O'ahu.
- Wave modeling for O'ahu and the main Hawaiian Islands.
- Swell patterns used in traditional Marshallese navigation.
- Wave-induced current modeling, radiation stress, Wave induced setup over reefs.
- Wave-induced mixing over the continental shelf.

06/2002 -11/2002 Principal investigator : Pierre Flament, *University of Hawai'i, Department of Oceanography* :

- Surface currents and surface waves measurements using an HF radar, in the Kauai'i channel.
- Surface currents and surface waves measurements using an HF radar, in the Adriatic Sea.

07/1997 – 07/1998 Principal investigator : Peter V. Ridd, *James Cook University, Physics Department, Townsville, Australia*

- Hydrodynamic modeling in a mangrove and salt flats fringed tidal creek in North Queensland, Australia.

09/1997 – 10/1997 Principal investigator : Pr. Mal Heron, *James Cook University, Physics Department, Townsville, Australia*

- Surface Currents measurements using HF Radar in the Northern Territories, Australia.

02/1997 - 06/1997 Principal investigator : Dr Gurvan Madec, *Laboratoire d'Océanographie Dynamique et de Climatologie (LODYC), Paris, France*

- Programming of the rotation between z and sigma surface of the lateral diffusion term in the OPA 8 OGCM.
- Comparative analysis of the effect of the lateral diffusion on the surfacing of the equatorial Undercurrent.

PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS

39 : Jullien, S.; **Aucan, J.**; Lefèvre, J.; Peltier, A.; and Menkes, C.E.: Tropical cyclone induced wave setup around New Caledonia during cyclone COOK (2017). *J. of Coastal Res.*, 2020, Special Issue No. 95, pp. 50-54

38 : Sous D., Tissier M., Rey V., Touboul J., Bouchette F., Devenon J. L., Chevalier Cristèle, **Aucan Jérôme**. Wave transformation over a barrier reef. *Continental Shelf Research*, 2019, 184, p. 66-80. ISSN 0278-4343

37 : Howe B. M., Arbic B. K., **Aucan Jérôme**, Barnes C. R., Bayliff N., Becker N., Butler R., Doyle L., Elipot S., Johnson G. C., Landerer F., Lentz S., Luther D. S., Muller M., Mariano J., Panayotou K., Rowe C., Ota H., Song Y. T., Thomas M., Thomas P. N., Thompson P., Tilmann F., Weber T., Weinstein S., Joint Task Force for SMART Cables. SMART Cables for observing the global ocean : science and implementation. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 2019, 6, p. art. 424 [27 p.].

36 : Cocquempot Lucie, Delacourt Christophe, Paillet Jerome, Riou Philippe, **Aucan Jérôme**, Castelle Bruno, Charria Guillaume, Claudet Joachim, Conan Pascal, Coppola Laurent, Hocdé Régis, Planes Serge, Raimbault Patrick, Savoye Nicolas, Testut Laurent, Vuillemin Renaud (2019). Coastal Ocean and Nearshore Observation: A French Case Study. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6(324), 17p. Publisher's official version : <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00324>

35 : Roger J., Pelletier B., **Aucan J.** (2019). Update of the tsunami catalogue of New Caledonia using a decision table based on seismic data and maregraphic records. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences Discussions*, 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-2019-36>

34 : **Aucan Jérôme**, Hoeke R. K., Storlazzi C. D., Stopa J., Wandres M., Lowe R. Waves do not contribute to global sea-level rise. *Nature Climate Change*, 2019, 9 (1), p. 2-2. ISSN 1758-678X

- 33 : Butler R., and **J. Aucan** : The Aloha Cabled Observatory: New Insights into hurricane generation of the seismo-acoustic noise spectrum, *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 2018, 144(3), p1957, doi: 10.1121/1.5068554
- 32 : **Aucan, J.** : Effects of Climate Change on Sea Levels and Inundation Relevant to the Pacific Islands. Pacific Marine Climate Change Report Card: [Science Review 2018, pp 43-49.](#)
- 31: Butler R., and **J. Aucan** : Multisensor, Microseismic Observations of a Hurricane Transit near the Aloha Cabled Observatory. [Journal of Geophysical Research, Solid Earth, 123, 3027–3046](#), 2017.
- 30: Kumar V., Melet A., Meyssignac B., Ganachaud A., **Aucan J.** and Singh A. : Reconstruction of local sea-levels at south west Pacific islands - a multiple linear regression approach (1979-2014), [Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans, 123, 2018.](#)
- 29: **Aucan J.**, Vende-Leclerc M., Dumas P. and Bricquie M. : Wave forcing and morphological changes of the New Caledonia lagoon islets, [Comptes Rendus Geosciences, 2017.](#)
- 28: **Aucan J.**, M. A. Merrifield and N. Pouvreau : Historical sea level in the South Pacific from rescued archives, geodetic measurements and satellite altimetry, [Pure And applied Geophysics, 2017.](#)
- 27: Howe, B. M., **J. Aucan**, and F. Tilmann : Submarine cable systems for future societal needs, *Eos*, 97, doi:10.1029/2016EO056781, 2016.
- 26: Koch-Larrouy A., Atmadipoera A., Van Beek P., Madec G., **Aucan J.**, Lyard F., Grelet J., and M. Souhaut : Estimates of tidal mixing in the Indonesian archipelago from multidisciplinary INDOMIX in-situ data, *Deep-Sea Research part I*, 106, 2015.
- 25: Cravatte S., Kestenare E., Eldin G., Ganachaud A., Lefèvre J., Marin F., Menkes C., and **Aucan, J.** : Regional circulation around New Caledonia from two decades of observations, *Journal of Marine Systems*, 2015.
- 24: Andréfouët, S., **J. Aucan**, H. Jourdan, P. Kench, C. Menkes, E. Vidal, and H. Yamano : Conservation of low-islands: high priority despite sea-level rise. A comment on Courchamp et al. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 2015.
- 23: Rawat A., F. Ardhuin, V. Ballu, W. Crawford, C. Corela, and **J. Aucan**, 2014: Infragravity waves across the oceans. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 2014
- 22: Ardhuin F, Rawat A., and **Aucan J.** : A numerical model for free infragravity waves: definition and validation at regional and global scales. *Ocean Modelling*, 2014.
- 21: **Aucan J.** and F.Ardhuin : Infragravity waves in the deep ocean : An upward révision. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 2013.
- 20: Ardhuin F., Lavanant T., Obrebski M., Marie L., Royer J.Y., d’Eu J.F., Howe B., Lukas R., and **J. Aucan** : A numerical model for ocean ultra low frequency noise: wave-generated acoustic-gravity and Rayleigh modes. *J. of the Acoustical Society of America*, 2013.
- 19: **Aucan J.** and W. Llovel : Deep water trends and variability at the BATS site in the Subtropical North Atlantic and consequences on local sea level budget. *Deep Sea Research II*. 2013.
- 18: Casey J.R., **Aucan J.**, Goldberg S.R., and Lomas M. W. : Changes in partitioning of carbon amongst photosynthetic pico- and nano-plankton groups in the Sargasso Sea in response to changes in the North Atlantic Oscillation. *Deep Sea Research II*. 2013.
- 17: **Aucan J.**, Hoeke R.H., and Merrifield M.A. : Wave-driven sea level anomalies at the Midway tide gauge as an indicator of the North Pacific Storminess over the past 50 years. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 2012.
- 16: Duennebie F., R. Lukas, E.M. Nosal, **J. Aucan**, and R. Weller : Wind, waves and background Acoustic levels at station Aloha, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 117, 2012
- 15: Vetter O., J.M. Becker, M.A. Merrifield, A-C Pequignet, **J. Aucan**, S.J. Boc, and C.E. Pollock : Wave setup over a Pacific Island fringing reef, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 115, 2010.
- 14: Genz J., **J. Aucan**, M. Merrifield, B. Finney, K. Joel, and A. Kelen : Wave Navigation in The Marshall Islands: Comparing Indigenous and Western Scientific Knowledge of the Ocean, *Oceanography*, 22, 2009.
- 13: Pequignet A.C., Becker J. M., Merrifield M. A. and **J. Aucan** : Forcing of resonant modes on a fringing reef during tropical storm Man-Yi, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 36, 2009.

- 12: Caldwell P.C., **J. Aucan** and S. Vitousek : Frequency and Duration of Coinciding High Surf and Tides along the North Shore of Oahu, Hawaii 1981-2007, *Journal of Coastal Research*, 25(3), 734-743, 2009.
- 11: **Aucan J.** and M. Merrifield : Boundary mixing associated with tidal and near-inertial internal waves, *Journal of Physical Oceanography* 38, p.1238–1252, 2008.
- 10: Becker J. M., Y. L. Firing, **J. Aucan**, R. Holman, and M. Merrifield : Video-based Observations of Nearshore Sand Ripples and Ripple Migration, *Journal of Geophysical Research* 112, 2007.
- 9: Caldwell P.C. and **J. Aucan** : An Empirical Method for Estimating Surf Heights from Deep Water Significant Wave Heights and Peak Periods in Coastal Zones with Narrow Shelves, Steep Bottom Slopes, and High Refraction. *Journal of Coastal Research*, 23(5) 1237-1244, 2007
- 8: **Aucan, J.** : Directional Wave Climatology for the Hawaiian Islands from Buoy Data and the Influence of ENSO on Extreme Wave Events from Model Hindcast. 9th International Workshop on Wave Hindcasting and Forecasting. JCOMM Technical Report No. 34 / WMO-TD. No. 1368. 2006
- 7: **Aucan J.**, Merrifield, M., Luther, D. and P. Flament. : Deep mixing events along the flanks of the Hawaiian ridge. *Journal of Physical Oceanography* 36, p.1202-1219, 2006.
- 6: Garces, M., Fee, D., McNamara, S., **Aucan, J.** and Merrifield, M. : The deep sound of one wave plunging, *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 120, 3032-3032, 2006.
- 5: **Aucan J.**, Fee D. and M. Garces : Infrasonic estimation of surf period, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 33(5) 2006.
- 4: M. Garces, **J. Aucan**, D. Fee, P. Caron, M. Merrifield, R. Gibson, J. Bhattacharyya, and S. Shah : Infrasound from large surf, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 2006.
- 3: Garces M., Fee D., Carron P., Hetzer C., **Aucan J.**, Merrifield M., Gibson R. and J. Bhattacharyya : Multi parameter studies of surf infrasound, *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 117, 2452, 2005.
- 2: Garces M., Hetzer C., Merrifield M., Willis M., and **J. Aucan** : Observations of surf infrasound in Hawai'i, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 30(24), 2003.
- 1: **Aucan J.**, and Ridd P. V. : Tidal asymmetry in creeks surrounded by salt-flats and mangroves with small swamp slopes, *Wetlands Ecology and Management*, Kluwer Academic Publishers 223-231, 2000.

CHAPTERS IN BOOKS

- Claude E. Payri, Valérie Allain, **Jérôme Aucan**, Corine David, Victor David, Cyril Dutheil, Lionel Loubersac, Christophe Menkes, Bernard Pelletier, Gilles Pestana, Sarah Samadi, Chapter 27 - New Caledonia, Editor(s): Charles Sheppard, *World Seas: an Environmental Evaluation (Second Edition)*, Academic Press, 2019, Pages 593-618, ISBN 9780081008539, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100853-9.00035-X>.
- Aucan Jérôme** (coord.). Des récifs impactés mais résistants : partie 3. In : Payri Claude (ed.), Moatti Jean-Paul (pref.). *Nouvelle-Calédonie : archipel de corail*. Marseille (FRA) ; Nouméa : IRD ; Solaris, 2018, p. 145-177. ISBN 978-2-7099-2632-4
- Douillet Pascal, **Aucan Jérôme**, Lefèvre J., Le Gendre R., Desclaux T., Drouzy M. La valse des masses d'eau dans le lagon néo-calédonien. In : Payri Claude (ed.), Moatti Jean-Paul (pref.). *Nouvelle-Calédonie : archipel de corail*. Marseille (FRA) ; Nouméa : IRD ; Solaris, 2018, p. 39-46. ISBN 978-2-7099-2632-4
- Aucan Jérôme**, Menkès Christophe, Martinez Jean-Michel. What are the signs of current climate change ?. In : Reinert M., Janicot Serge (ed.), Aubertin Catherine (ed.), Bernoux Martial (ed.), Dounias Edmond (ed.), Guégan Jean-François (ed.), Lebel Thierry (ed.), Mazurek Hubert (ed.), Sultan Benjamin (ed.), Sokona Y. (pref.), Moatti Jean-Paul (pref.). *Climate change : what challenges for the South ?*. Marseille : IRD, 2015, p. 33-41. (Beaux-Livres). ISBN 978-2-7099-2172-5
- David Gilbert, **Aucan Jérôme**, Guiral Daniel, Andréfouët Serge, Cormier Salem Marie-Christine. Coastal and island zones : areas under anthropic pressure. In : Reinert M., Janicot Serge (ed.), Aubertin Catherine (ed.), Bernoux Martial (ed.), Dounias Edmond (ed.), Guégan Jean-François (ed.), Lebel Thierry (ed.), Mazurek Hubert (ed.), Sultan Benjamin (ed.), Sokona Y. (pref.), Moatti Jean-Paul (pref.). *Climate change : what challenges for the South ?*. Marseille : IRD, 2015, p. 101-113. (Beaux-Livres). ISBN 978-2-7099-2172-5

TEACHING EXPERIENCE

- Lecturer, General Oceanography POGO module , Introduction to Physical Oceanography (BIOS, 2009)
- Lecturer (surface waves, tides and internal waves), part of OCN 620 Physical Oceanography (University of Hawaii, 2008)
- Teaching Assistant, OCN 201, Introduction to Oceanography (University of Hawaii, 1999)
- Teaching Assistant, elementary physics, James Cook University (1998)

STUDENT SUPERVISION

- Vandhna Kumar : PhD co-advisor (2014-2017), LEGOS Toulouse, CERFACS Toulouse and University of the South Pacific (Fiji) : Reconstruction of local sea-levels at south west Pacific islands – a multiple linear regression approach
- Oriane Bruyère : BSc Intern (2017), University of New Caledonia. Calibration procedure and validation of nearshore temperature and pressure sensors
- Assaf Azouri : PhD Committee (2016), University of Hawaii : Observations, Forecast, And Modeling Of 0.5-200 Min Infragravity Oscillations In Hale'iwa Harbor Region, Hawai'i
- Julie Plantaz : MSc Intern (2016), University of Grenoble : Methods analysis and creation of a directional wave climatology for New Caledonia
- Thibault Garnier : MSc Intern (2016), University of Bordeaux : Implementation and validation against in-situ data of a numerical Tsunami model for New Caledonia
- Barbara Patoit : MSc Intern (2015), ENSTA Bretagne : Modeling of waves under intense tropical cyclones in the Southwest Pacific : the example of Cyclone Pam in March 2015.
- Raphaëlle Huth : MSc intern (2013), University of Marseille, France : Impact of short term changes in light intensity on surface chlorophyll concentration from ocean color product.
- Rosie Oglethorpe, BIOS intern (2009) from Cambridge, UK : Estimates of mixing from the Bermuda Atlantic Time-series Study (BATS) CTD data, using a Thorpe scale analysis.
- Rebecca Jackson, BIOS intern (2009) from Yale, USA : Design, construction, deployment and data analysis of a temperature profiling mooring to investigate internal seiches and waves in a strongly stratified, semi-enclosed basin in Bermuda.

ACADEMIC SERVICE AND EXPERTISE

- Reviewer of publications submitted to : Journal of Physical Oceanography, Journal of Geophysical Research, Marine pollution bulletin, Journal of Coastal research, Coral Reefs, Science Advances.
- Reviewer of research proposals submitted to funding agencies : NSF (USA), ANR (France).
- Member of the French Oceanographic Fleet commission CNFH (evaluation of national ship time requests), for 2 terms (2010-2014 and 2014-2018) as evaluator, then co-chair of the commission (2018-2022). Co-author of the French Oceanographic Fleet prospective white paper (2017).
- Science and Society Committee Chair for the Joint Task Force to investigate the use of submarine telecommunications cables for ocean and climate monitoring and disaster warning (since 2016).
- Chair of the Pacific Islands Countries and Territories Regional working group of the Pacific Tsunami Warning System, ICG/PTWS (since 2019).
- Designated expert and national delegate for New Caledonia at the Intergovernmental Coordination Group meetings of the Pacific Tsunami Warning System, ICG/PTWS (since 2014).
- National delegate for Bermuda at the Intergovernmental Coordination Group meetings of the Tsunami and other Coastal Hazards Warning System for the Caribbean and Adjacent Regions, ICG/CARIBE (2009-2010).
- Scientist-in-charge for the Pacific Region for the Sea-Surface-Salinity (SSS) observatory from Voluntary Observing Ships (2012-2019).

-Co-Organizer of Second DBCP Pacific Islands Training Workshop on Ocean Observations and Data Applications, JCOMM IOC/WMO, Noumea, May 2016.

COMMUNICATIONS AT NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC MEETINGS

Sylvie Fiat, David Varillon, Bernard Pelletier, **Jérôme Aucan**, Régis Hocdé : ReefTEMPS, Network of coastal oceanic sensors, Open access data portal, Research Data Alliance 15th Plenary meeting, Melbourne 2020.

Kong, LSL, Howe, BM., Arbic, BK. , **Aucan, J** , Barnes, C , Bayliff, N , Becker, N , Butler, R , Doyle, L , Elipot, S , Johnson, GC (I, Landerer, F , Lentz, S , Luther, DS , Muller, M , Mariano, J, Panayotou, K, Rowe, C , Ota, H , Song, YT , Thomas, M, Thomas, PN., Thompson, P, Tilmann, F, Weber, T, Weinstein, S, Joint Task Force for SMART Cables : SMART Cables for Observing the Global Ocean: Overview and Implementation. OceanObs'19, Honolulu 2019.

Howe, B, **Aucan, J**, Baumann-Pickering, S, D'Asaro, E, Di Iorio, D, Elipot, S, Ferrari, R, Fisher, A, Harris, R, Heimbach, P, Hughes, C, Jannsen, F, Katsumata, K, Legg, S, Luther, D, Moum, J, Pinkel, R, Ray, R , Ruhl, H, Soule, A, Thurnherr, A, Watts, DR, Weller, R, Wheat, G, Zumberg, M : Physics Essential Ocean Variables in the Deep Ocean Observing Strategy. OceanObs'19, Honolulu 2019.

Aucan Jerome, Brian K. Arbic, Shane Elipot , Bruce M. Howe , Gregory C. Johnson , Felix Landerer, Douglas S. Luther, Malte Muller, Y. Tony Song, Maik Thomas, Philip Thompson, Tobias Weber : SMART Cables for Observing the Global Ocean: Climate, Sea Level, Circulation, Tides and Waves. OceanObs'19, Honolulu 2019.

Cocquempot, L, Delacourt, C, Paillet, J, Riou, P, **Aucan, J**, Castelle, B, Charria, G, Claudet, J, Conan, P, Coppola, L, Hocde, R, Planes, S , Raimbault, P , Savoye, N, Testut, L , Vuillemin, R : Coastal Ocean and Nearshore Observation: A French Case Study. OceanObs'19, Honolulu 2019.

Aucan J. Howe B. SMART submarine telecommunication cables to monitor sea level in the global ocean. IAPSO 2017 Joint assembly , Cape Town 2017 .

Aucan J. : Tide gauge and opportunistic observations of tsunamis along exposed and sheltered coastlines of New Caledonia . International Tsunami Workshop. Tahiti French Polynesia, 2017.

Aucan J. : Territoires Ultra Marins: défis et enjeux (*French Overseas Territories : Challenges and stakes*) (invited). LEFE/GMMC, Toulon 2016.

Aucan J. : Recherche et Marégraphie (*Research and sea-level measurements*) (invited). Journées Refmar SHOM, UNESCO Paris 2016.

Bruce M Howe, James T Potemra, Rhatt Butler, Fernando Santiago-Mandujano, Roger Lukas, Frederick K Duennebie, David M Karl and **Jerome Aucan** : Continuing and New Measurements at the Abyssal ALOHA Cabled Observatory, AGU-ASLO Ocean Sciences Meeting 2016.

Valerie Ballu, Stephane Calmant, Pierre Valty, Médéric Gravelle, Pierre Sakic, **Jerome Aucan** and Bernard Pelletier : Horizontal and vertical deformation field in New Caledonia, South West Pacific, derived from more than 20 years of GNSS measurements. AGU Fall Meeting 2015.

Ballu, V., S. Calmant, **J. Aucan**, V. Duvat-Magnan, B. Pelletier, M. Gravelle, C. Shum, M. Karpytchev, M. Becker, F. Hossain, P. Simeoni, and P. Valty, Coastal vulnerability to climate change-induced sea-level rise may be increased by land motion and human factors, Our Common Future Under Climate Change International Scientific Conference, Paris, France, July 7–10, 2015.

Biegala I, **Aucan J.**, Desnues A., Clavere-Graciette A., Raimbault P. : The South Pacific ocean time series (SPOT) station: a first focus on diazotrophs community. ASLO, Honolulu, 2014.

Arshad Rawat, Fabrice Arduin, and **Jerome Aucan** : Infragravity waves across the oceans. EGU, Vienna 2014.

Damien SOUS, **Jérôme Aucan**, Jean BLANCHOT, Jean Luc DEVENON, Marc PAGANO, et al.. Field study of cross-reef dynamics above the Ouano coral barrier, New Caledonia, France. 24e Réunion des Sciences de la Terre, 2014,

Christèle Chevalier , **Jérôme Aucan**, Jean Blanchot, Jean-Luc Devenon, Marc Pagano, Vincent Rey, Gilles Rougier and Damien Sous : Impact of cross-reef fluxes on the Ouano lagoon circulation, Joint Numerical Sea Modelling Group meeting, 2014.

Rawat A., Arduin F., **J. Aucan** : Analysis of the global free infra-gravity wave climate for the SWOT satellite mission, and preliminary results of numerical modeling. AGU 2012, San Francisco.

Aucan J. and W. Llovel : Deep water trends and variability at the BATS site in the Subtropical North Atlantic and consequences on local sea level budget. AGU 2012, San Francisco.

Aucan J. and N. Pouvreau : Sea-Level observations in Nouméa 1967-present. SOPAC/STAR meeting, 2012, Nouméa New Caledonia.

Aucan J. The “Free Infragravity” Wave Climate Measured by a Global Network of Bottom Pressure recorders. 12th international workshop on wave hindcasting and forecasting, 2011, Hawaii.

Casey, J., Lomas, M., and **J. Aucan** interannual dynamics of carbon partitioning within the sargasso sea picoplankton assemblage. ASLO meeting 2011 Puerto Rico.

J. Genz, **J. Aucan**, B. Finney, M. Merrifield Spectral Wave Modeling of Swell Transformations in Indigenous Marshallese Navigation; 10h international workshop on wave hindcasting and forecasting, 2009, Hawaii.

Mark Merrifield, A-C Pequignet, J. Becker, **J. Aucan**, O. Vetter, T. Hilmer, S. Boc, C. Pollock, K.-F. Cheung, J. Goo, P. Quiroga & Y. Wu. Waves and Water Level Collected During the Pacific Island Land Ocean Typhoon Experiment; 10h international workshop on wave hindcasting and forecasting, 2009, Hawaii.

Pequignet, A C N, Becker, J M, Merrifield, M A, and **Aucan, J** : Wave Forced Normal Modes on Fringing Reefs. AGU Fall Meeting 2008.

Aucan J., Pequignet A. C., Vetter O. J., Becker, J. M. and M.A. Merrifield : Wave Transformation and Setup across Ipan Reef, Guam, During Tropical Storm Man-YI. ALSO Ocean Sciences Meeting 2008, Orlando, Florida.

Hoeke, R. K. and **J. Aucan** : Sea-Level Rise, Flooding, Flushing and wave heights at a Coral Atoll. ALSO Ocean Sciences Meeting 2008, Orlando, Florida.

Aucan J. : Directional Wave Climatology for the Hawaiian Islands from Buoy Data and the Influence of ENSO on Extreme Wave Events from Model Hindcast, 9th international workshop on wave hindcasting and forecasting, 2006, Victoria, Canada.

Firing Y. L., **J. Aucan**, M. A. Merrifield and J. M. Becker : Extreme water level decomposition. WCRP Understanding Sea Level Rise and Variability Workshop, UNESCO, Paris, 2006 (poster).

Aucan J. : Mixing along deep boundaries at the Kaena Ridge, AGU Ocean sciences meeting 2006, Honolulu, Hawaii.

Aucan J., M. Merrifield and D. Luther : Tidal mixing events on the deep flanks of Kaena Ridge, Hawaii. Dynamic Planet 2005, Cairns, Australia.

Aucan J., M. Merrifield, D. Luther, and P. Flament : Deep mixing events along the Hawaiian ridge, IAPSO / SCOR Ocean Mixing Conference, 2004, Victoria, Canada (poster).

Aucan J. : Effect of along-shore tidal currents on waves : around an the island of O'ahu, Hawaii, 8th international workshop on wave hindcasting and forecasting, 2004, Oahu, Hawaii.

Aucan J. : Merrifield, M.; Luther, D. The bottom boundary layer over the Flanks of the Hawaiian Ridge. EGU General Assembly, 2004, Nice, France.

Aucan J. : M. Merrifield, D. Luther, and P. Flament : Variabilité semi-diurne près de topographies sous marines abruptes et côtières: Assises de la Recherche Francaise dans le Pacifique. Nouméa 2004.

OTHER MEETINGS, PRESENTATIONS OR WORKSHOP

- Twenty-seventh Session of the Intergovernmental Coordination Group for the Pacific Tsunami Warning and Mitigation System (ICG/PTWS-XXVII) , Papeete, March 2017.
- Trilateral FRANZ (France-Australia-New Zealand) Seminar : Nouméa Nov. 2016
- PTWS SouthWest Pacific Working Group Honiara, Aug. 2016
- Trilateral FRANZ (France-Australia-New Zealand) Seminar : Nouméa Oct. 2015
- First DBCP Pacific Islands Training Workshop on Ocean Observations and Data Applications, JCOMM IOC/WMO, Palau May 2015.
- Twenty-sixth Session of the Intergovernmental Coordination Group for the Pacific Tsunami Warning and Mitigation System (ICG/PTWS-XXVI) , Honolulu, April 2015.
- United Nations Conference on Small Islands Developing States, Samoa, 2014.
- Regional Training Workshop on the PTWC Enhanced Products , Fiji, May 2014.
- Regional Exchanges SOPAC/CPS : Improvement of the tsunami warning systems in the French Overseas territory of New Caledonia and French Polynesia. 2012.
- Fifth Session of the Intergovernmental Coordination Group for Tsunami and Other Coastal Hazards Warning System for the Caribbean and Adjacent Regions. Nicaragua, March 2010.
- Fourth Session of the Intergovernmental Coordination Group for Tsunami and Other Coastal Hazards Warning System for the Caribbean and Adjacent Regions. Martinique, June 2009.

- Workshop on the South West Pacific Ocean Circulation and its relation with climate. Cairns, Australia, August 2005.
- Third Session of the Intergovernmental Coordination Group for the Indian Ocean Tsunami Warning and Mitigation System, Bali, Indonesia, August 2006.

OCEANOGRAPHIC CRUISES

03/2015	<i>Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Flores</i>
Recovery of ADCP cage off the coast of Peru		
08/2014	<i>Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Kilo Moana</i>
Deployment of a new science package on the Aloha Cabled Observatory (ACO)		
02/2014	<i>Chief Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Kilo Kai</i>
Recovery of deep Bottom Pressure Recorders (Oahu, Hawaii)		
11/2013	<i>Chief Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Huki Pono</i>
Deployment of deep Bottom Pressure Recorders (Oahu, Hawaii)		
02/2013	<i>Chief Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Alis</i>
SPOT #2 Fixed point sampling cruise in the SouthWest Pacific		
10/2012	<i>Chief Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Alis</i>
SPOT #1 Fixed point sampling cruise in the SouthWest Pacific		
09/2010	<i>Scientist / deck operations</i>	<i>R/V Atlantic Explorer</i>
OFP subsurface mooring deployment/recovery cruise		
04/2009	<i>Scientist / deck operations</i>	<i>R/V Atlantic Explorer</i>
OFP subsurface mooring deployment/recovery cruise		
03/2009	<i>Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Atlantic Explorer</i>
BATS Cruise # 245, CTD sampling, Plankton Tows, drifting arrays deployments.		
02/2009	<i>Chief Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Klaus Wyrcki</i>
Recovery/Redeployment of Profiling mooring on Oahu's South Shore		
11/2008	<i>Chief Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Klaus Wyrcki</i>
Deployment of Profiling mooring on Oahu's South Shore		
08/2008	<i>Scientist</i>	<i>R/V T.G. Thompson</i>
Aloha Cabled Observatory installation cruise		
06/2007	<i>Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Kilo Moana</i>
Assisted in the mooring recovery and redeployment WHOTS IV.		
09/2006	<i>Scientist</i>	<i>Fishing boat</i>
Conducted a traditional navigation techniques study in the Marshall Islands.		
06/2006	<i>Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Revelle</i>
Participated in the mooring recovery and redeployment. WHOTS III		
08/2005	<i>Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Melville</i>
Participated in the mooring recovery and redeployment. WHOTS II		
10/2003	<i>Chief Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Kilo Moana</i>
North Hawai'i ridge deep benthic mixing		
11/2003	<i>Chief Scientist</i>	<i>R/V Kilo Moana</i>
South Hawai'i ridge deep benthic mixing		
07/2003	<i>Research Assistant</i>	<i>R/V Revelle</i>
Hawaii Ocean Mixing Experiment (HOME), Subsurface moorings recoveries		

08/2002 *Research Assistant*
Hawaii Ocean Mixing Experiment, Subsurface moorings deployments *R/V Wecoma*

2000 to 2008 *Chief Scientist*
Numerous deployment/recovery cruises aboard various work boats, for the deployment and maintenance of 3 nearshore datawell directional wave buoys around the Hawaiian Islands *Various ships*

FIELD INSTRUMENT DEPLOYMENT EXPERIENCE

2019 New Caledonia
Wave buoy deployment and data management

2018-2019 Fiji
Wave buoy and temperature mooring deployment and data management

2018-2019 French Polynesia
Bottom mounted pressure sensor deployment, scuba dive and low-tide land deployments

2016-2020 New Caledonia
Bottom mounted pressure sensor deployment, scuba dive and low-tide land deployments in the SouthWest of New Caledonia (EMIL project)

2015 Peru
ADCP trawl resistant cage recovery, using an ROV.

2012-2014 New Caledonia
Bottom mounted pressure sensor deployment, scuba dive and low-tide land deployments on the East Coast and Loyalty Islands of New Caledonia

2011-2012 Honolulu, HI :
Bottom mounted pressure sensor deployment with a free-falling, recoverable, bottom landing frame.

2008-2009 Honolulu, HI
Subsurface profiling mooring (McLane MMP).

2007-2008 Guam, Saipan, CNMI
Pacific Island Land-Ocean Typhoon Experiment (PILOT). Multiple deployments, recoveries and data analysis of bottom mounted pressure sensors, current meters, and offshore wave buoys.

2006 Indonesia
Maintenance of GLOSS Sea-Level monitoring stations on the Islands of Bali and Sumatra.

2005 Barking Sands Kauai'I, HI
Underwater bottom mounted pressure sensors for infrasound experiment

2005 Kailua-Kona, HI
Underwater bottom mounted pressure sensors for infrasound experiment

2004 Oahu, HI
HF radar deployment, PI : Pierre Flament

2004 Venice, Italy
HF radar deployment, PI : Pierre Flament

1999 – 2000 Kailua Bay, HI
Underwater bottom mounted pressure sensors for wave attenuation over reef study

2001 – 2002 Waimea Bay, HI
Underwater bottom mounted pressure sensors for wave run-up study, 2001

2002 Waimea Bay, Oahu (deployed from the R/V Kilo Moana).
Thermistor chain and pressure gages mooring for a nearshore internal wave study

1998 Townsville, Australia
Pressure sensors and current meters deployed in a tidal estuary, PI : Peter V. Ridd

1998 Northern territories, Australia
HF-Radar deployment, PI : Mal Heron

COMPUTER SKILLS

- Operating systems : Linux, Unix (solaris), MacOS.
- Programming languages : Matlab, csh, C, fortran, GMT, Perl.
- Communication language with Oceanographic Instruments (RDI, Datawell, Seabird, Nortek, InterOcean)

OTHER PUBLICATIONS

- Aucan Jerome, Rolin Jean-Francois, Loubersac Lionel (2017). Vers des câbles sous-marins « intelligents ». Pourquoi la Nouvelle-Calédonie est-elle concernée ? (*Toward "SMART" undersea Cables, Why should New Caledonia be concerned*) Tai Kona , (17), 22-36 . Open Access version : <http://archimer.ifremer.fr/doc/00384/49566/>
- Olagnon Michel, Loubersac Lionel, Aucan Jérôme (2014). Les vagues scélérates. (*Rogues Waves*) Tai Kona, (7), 26-40. Open Access version : <http://archimer.ifremer.fr/doc/00186/29724/>
- Oeil Magazine #6 (2014)
- Oeil magazine #5 (2013)
- The buoys don't lie, Scientist have developed several ways to measure the waves, Freesurf Magazine (2006)
- Sixth Sense of Surf, Freesurf Magazine (2006)
- What's a wave to do ? Scientists have many reasons to forecast the surf, Freesurf Magazine (2005)
- A tide to Ride, Tidal bores produce the world's longest rides, far from the ocean., Freesurf Magazine (2005)

AWARDS

- Townsville Port Authority price for achievement in Marine Physics 1998.

OUTREACH

- Jury "Science Academie". Southern Province , New Caledonia 2015
- Jury "Doctoriales". University of New Caledonia, 2015
- Public conference : Tsunamis in New Caledonia and the tsunami warning system. IRD Nouméa, 2013.
- Edsys Conference 2011 : Invited talk : Waves and Tsunami.
- Université du Temps libre du Rouerge 2011 : Invited lecture : Waves tides and tsunamis.
- Science fair judge, Oct 2004 and 2005, Kapolei middle school, Hawaii.
- Career Day, Oct. 2005, Kapolei Middle School, Hawaii.
- Surfrider Foundation, Hawaii Board of Director meeting. Presentation about wave climate and forecasting
- Guest Lecturer, "Waves, tides and tsunamis", Jul 2002, Jul 2005, July 2007, July 2008, Punahou high school, Hawaii.
- Wailua Wahiawa Rotary Club presentation on waves, tides and tsunamis, August 2007.

OTHER

- 6 years as sailing instructor and instructor trainee in Les Sables d'Olonne, France.
- 20 years of experience as race crew member, skipper-owner of Ho'okipa, a racing monohull based in Honolulu between 2007 and 2012, and based in Noumea since 2012, skipper on chartered 30-40' monohull cruisers in the Mediterranean and North Atlantic, and skipper on multihulls charters in New Caledonia
- Numerous travel in Asia in remote areas for installation of automated tsunami stations.

Régis HOCDE

Observatories, information systems, data science

Status **Research ingeener** 49 years old, 2 childs

Institute **IRD** - French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development www.ird.fr

MARBEC research unit (Univ. Montpellier, CNRS, IFREMER, IRD)
 MARine Biodiversity, Exploitation and Conservation www.umarbec.fr/en/

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 Port +33 (0) 6 66 90 87 02 - Tel +33 (0) 4 67 14 47 44 - regis.hocde@ird.fr

Web ORCID : [0000-0002-5794-2598](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5794-2598) - CV HAL : cv.archives-ouvertes.fr/regis-hocde
 CSS5-IRD: [Data and Model Sciences competencies of Regis Hocde](#)

Main missions

Present Position (since Dec 2016)	<p>Research ingeener, in MARBEC research unit</p> <p>⇒ <i>with focus on two main objectives :</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observatories and data sciences - Marine biodiversity / Communities’ dynamics and functioning <p>⇒ <i>Leader (co-PI) of main projects :</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lengguru 2017-2019 “Biodiversity assessment in reef twilight zone” project, in West Papua, Indonesia www.lengguru.org - Megafauna 2017-2020 "Isolated seamounts and island as the last refugia for marine megafauna: revealing the unseen biodiversity using environmental DNA - Selamat “International joint laboratory” project 2020-2024 <p>⇒ <i>National expert for several topics :</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research infrastructures & Scientific information system management - Scientific diving & closed-circuit rebreather
Since 2009 to Nov 2016	I has a dual function giving impulse and coordinating major projects :
Since 2016 to Nov 2016	‘Research infrastructures and observatories’ project leader, Scientific Direction, IRD
Since 2009 to 2015	Advisor to the Director General for Science of IRD, in charge of research infrastructures and observatories www.ird.fr
Since 2012 to ...	<p>“Lengguru” project co-coordinator and head of the marine components and of the data-management component www.lengguru.org/</p> <p>⇒ organization of the “Lengguru 2014” and “Lengguru 2017” expeditions in West Papua, Indonesia</p>
Since 2009 to 2017	<p>Scientific information systems projects manager - Deputy to the director of GOPS (South Pacific integrated observatory for the environment, terrestrial and marine biodiversity) www.gops-observatory.org/en/</p> <p>⇒ design and creation of a consortium (GIS) federating 17 universities and research organizations</p> <p>⇒ foundation of the “ReefTEMPS” sensor network, to monitor the coastal sea waters in the South and South-West Pacific region & management of the of the dedicated sensor information system reeftemps.observatoire-gops.org</p>

2005 – 2009	Scientific data-manager projects leader, creation of the common department of scientific computing, IRD
2003 - 2005	Engineer, in charge of the "Development of the applications of the program Seine-Aval (Estuary of the Seine), France ⇒ To apply and develop the results of the research of the program Seine-Aval (development of tools for decision-making aid / studies and expertises / management and valorisation of the research projects...)
1998 - 2003	Scientific management of the program Seine-Aval, Deputy to the scientific director (Estuary of the Seine), France
1997 - 1998	Management of environmental studies, Atlantic littoral and Channel Director of OCEADE organization (Organisme de Conseil, d'Etude et d'Aide à la Décision en Environnement), Brest, France
1995-1996	Environmental study (Management plan of the Rade de Brest), Bay of Brest, France Engineer, OXYGENE organization, France
1991-1995	Organization of oceanographic scientific missions - on land or on board – in coastal area of foreign countries: Tunisia, Libya, Yemen, Mozambique, etc. – With by diving activities: marine biodiversity, ecology, pharmacology, archeology.

Developed skills

1. Steering and coordination of projects and structures
2. Management of teams and collaborations
3. Technical expertise in scientific data management and information systems
4. Scientific Expertise in estuaries and coastal environment / marine biodiversity
5. Specific Competence: Professional Diving (with closed circuit rebreather CCR)

Initial training

University course in Environment, biology and marine ecology, with geomatics, remote sensing and signal processing specialty units.

Past and Current duties

Scientific Committees, Research unit evaluation committees, Expertises, International working groups.

Others skills

Capacity building of scientific counterparts In Indonesia, island countries of South Pacific, Columbia.

Organization of scientific expeditions, Oceanographic missions & hyperbaric activities (since 1989 to 2020: on coasts of many foreign countries).

Supervision of staffs, supervision of research students (service creation, team building, transversal management. Supervision of research students).

Communications for large public, interviews (press, TV documentary)

Several TV documentaries (scientific advisor), international and national press and medias.

Teachings and educational activities

Publications (Excluding expert and technical reports)

Several publications in 3 topics: i. Observation network, Scientific information systems and Data-Management, ii. Marine biodiversity, Ecology and Environment, iii. Diving methods.

2020

Kadariusman, H.Y. Sugeha, L. Pouyaud, R. Hocdé, I.B. Hismayasari, E. Gunaisah, S.B. Widiarto, G. Arafat, F. Widyasari, D. Mouillot and E. Paradis, 2020. 'A thirteen-million-year divergence between two lineages of Indonesian coelacanth'. *Scientific Reports*. vol. 10, no. 1. p. 192. doi: [10.1038/s41598-019-57042-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-57042-1).

— — —, 2020. 'Publisher Correction: A thirteen-million-year divergence between two lineages of Indonesian coelacanth'. *Scientific Reports*. vol. 10, no. 1. p. 4641. doi: [10.1038/s41598-020-61557-3](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-61557-3).

Delrieu-Trottin, E., J. Durand, G. Limmon, T. Sukmono, Kadariusman, H.Y. Sugeha, W. Chen, F. Busson, P. Borsa, H. Dahrudin, S. Sauri, Y. Fitriana, M.S.A. Zein, R. Hocdé, L. Pouyaud, P. Keith, D. Wowor, D. Steinke, R. Hanner and N. Hubert, 2020. 'Biodiversity inventory of the grey mullets (Actinopterygii: Mugilidae) of the Indo-Australian Archipelago through the iterative use of DNA-based species delimitation and specimen assignment methods'. *Evolutionary Applications*. p. evo.12926. doi: [10.1111/eva.12926](https://doi.org/10.1111/eva.12926).

ReefTEMPS, Network of coastal oceanic sensors, Open access data portal (2020). Sylvie Fiat, David Varillon, Bernard Pelletier, Jérôme Aucan, Régis Hocdé. Research Data Alliance (RDA) RDA's 15th Plenary Meeting, 18 - 20 March 2020 in Melbourne, Australia.

Deter Julie, Juhel Jean-Baptiste, Boulanger Emilie, Guellati Nacim, Mauron Stephen, Holon Florian, Mouillot David, Hocdé Régis (2020). Gombessa 5 cruise: CTD profiles in western Mediterranean, July 2019. SEANOE. DOI : [10.17882/71814](https://doi.org/10.17882/71814)

2019

Cocquempot, L., C. Delacourt, J. Paillet, P. Riou, J. Aucan, B. Castelle, G. Charria, J. Claudet, P. Conan, L. Coppola, R. Hocdé, S. Planes, P. Raimbault, N. Savoye, L. Testut and R. Vuillemin, 2019. 'Coastal Ocean and Nearshore Observation: A French Case Study'. *Frontiers in Marine Science*. vol. 6. p. 324. doi: [10.3389/fmars.2019.00324](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00324).

Fiat, S. and Hocdé, R., 'Critical Success Factors of the ReefTEMPS sensors-oriented environmental information system for a real operationality', presented at the Geospatial Sensing Conference 2019, Münster (Germany), 02-Sep-2019.

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- Norro A., Hocdé R.. 2017. A European competency level applied to the use of the closed circuit rebreather in scientific diving at work. First step. Highlighting the best practice. IIIrd European Conference on Scientific Diving (ECSD), 22-23 March 2017, Funchal, Madeira, Portugal.

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■ Refereed Journal Articles

Hocdé R., Fiat S. 2013. Le système d'information du « réseau de capteurs de température des eaux côtières dans la région du Pacifique Sud et Sud-Ouest, Netcom, Special issue « Les données environnementales en libre accès : politiques, expériences, usages », 27-1/2 | 2013, 170-173. [dx.doi.org/10.4000/netcom.1294](https://doi.org/10.4000/netcom.1294)

■ Edited Volumes & Book Chapters

Hocdé R. 2015. L'usage du CCR par la science : vers de nouvelles perspectives. In : Brun F., Bernabé P. Le guide de la plongée en recycleur. Challes-les-Eaux : Gap, 2015, p. 58-61. ISBN 978-2-7417-0567-3 [fdi:010067365 hal.ird.fr/ird-01394153](https://hal.ird.fr/ird-01394153)

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Dauvin J.C., K. Costil, S. Duhamel, R. Hocdé, P. Mouny, G. de Roton, N. Desroy, C. Le Neveu. 2002. Patrimoine biologique et chaînes alimentaires. Fascicule n°7, Ed. Ifremer, Programme Scientifique Seine-Aval, 48 p. borea.mnhn.fr/...PDF

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Hocdé R. antérieur à 2012 : Coordination de l'édition d'une collection de 16 fascicules thématiques. Domaines des systèmes d'information, des environnements estuariens et littoraux, des outils d'aide à la décision, de la gestion intégrée des zones côtières.

■ Peer-Reviewed Conference Articles & Abstracts

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- Fiat S., R. Hocdé. 2013. Collection des données de biodiversité marine de l'Indo Pacifique, IRD Nouméa. Séminaire Ecoscope: Vers un réseau d'observatoires de recherche sur la biodiversité - Quels enjeux et quelles avancées ?, 23-24 mai 2013, Paris.
- Fiat S., C. Payri, R. Hocdé. 2013. Lagplon, la base de données des plongeurs de l'IRD [Poster]. Séminaire Ecoscope: Vers un réseau d'observatoires de recherche sur la biodiversité - Quels enjeux et quelles avancées ?, 23-24 mai 2013, Paris.
- Hocdé R. et S. Fiat. 2013. Base de données IRD sur les observations sous-marines en Nouvelle-Calédonie (LAGPLON). Séminaire GBIF : Système Mondial d'Information sur la Biodiversité, 9 décembre 2013. Paris, France
- Chavagnac V., Monnin C., Ceuleneer G., Boulart C., Hoareau G., Pelletier B., Payri C., Hocdé R. and the HYDROPRONY Scientific Party. The characterization of hyperalkaline fluids in low temperature serpentinizing environments: Oman, Italy (Liguria), New Caledonia. SERPENTINE DAYS 3rd edition, 2-6 September, Porquerolles Islands (France), 2012.
- Postec A., Quémeneur M., Benaïssa F., Fardeau M.-L., Ollivier B., Erauso G. and "Hydroprony" Scientific Team. 2012, Microbial communities associated with alkaline hydrothermal systems of Prony Bay, New Caledonia: 14th International Symposium on Microbial Ecology, Copenhagen, Denmark, August 2012.
- Boulart C., B. Bourgeois, J. Butscher, V. Chavagnac, J. Colombet, L. Dombrowski, G. Erauso, D. Debroas, E. Folcher, E. Gérard, M. Gérard, R. Hocdé, B. Ménez, C. Monnin, B. Ollivier, C. B. Pelletier, C. Pisapia, A. Postec, M. Quémeneur, T. The alkaline hydrothermal field of the Prony Bay, New Caledonia, Serpentine Days workshop, Porquerolles, France, September 2012.
- Hocdé R. 2005. The Management Schemes in the Seine Estuary and the Seine Aval Programme. Paralia Nature Workshop : Management Schemes according to Article 6.1 of the Habitats Directive: Practical experience. Bruxelles, Belgique, 13-14 janvier 2005.
- Hocdé R. 2004. Aide à la décision et diffusion de l'information, quel rôle pour la recherche ? Colloque ISEMAR "Gestion intégrée des estuaires, ports de commerce et développement durable", Saint-Nazaire, 2 décembre 2004.
- Bodin N., A. Abarnou, V. Loizeau, A.M. Le Guellec, X. Philippon, X. Caisey, R. Hocdé, D. Latruite, M. Guillou. 2003. La contamination des crustacés décapodes par les PCB : comparaison Baie de Seine et Bretagne. [poster] Séminaire Seine-Aval, septembre 2003.
- Romaña L.A., R. Hocdé. 2002. An antagonist holding a mirror: the Seine estuary. ECSA Local Meeting : Ecological structures and functions in the Scheldt Estuary : from past to future. Anvers, Belgique, 7-10 octobre 2002.
- Lafite R., L.A. Romaña, R. Hocdé. 2001. How science can bring up knowledge and tools for management of estuarine environment : the case of the Seine estuary (France). Présentation à la Conférence de l'ERF 2001 : An Estuarine Odyssey, St Pete Beach, Floride, 4-8 Novembre 2001

■ Workshops, Symposia, and Seminars

- Hocdé R. 2012-2018. Numerous oral communications, organization of, participation in workshop within the "LENGGURU" project. (lead author)
- Hocdé R. 2006-2017. Numerous oral communications and participations in round tables, in the areas of data management, research infrastructures, South Pacific. (lead author)
- Hocdé R. 2001-2005. 10 communications orales en France, Belgique, aux Pays-Bas, USA. (en anglais ou français). Programme Seine-Aval. Domaine des environnements estuariens et littoraux, des outils d'aide à la décision, de la gestion intégrée des zones côtières. (auteur principal)

■ Other publications

Hocdé R. 2013. « Vers un label IRD des observatoires » Sciences au Sud - Le journal de l'IRD. n° 69 - April/May 2013

Pelletier B., R. Hocdé. 2013. « Le réseau ReefTEMPS ». Sciences au Sud - Le journal de l'IRD. n° 69 - April/May 2013

Pelletier B., Payri C., Folcher E., Butscher J., Bourgeois B., Erauso G., Postec A., Monnin C., Gérard M., Gérard E., Menez B., Guentas L., Hocdé R. Campagne HYDROPRONY du N.O. ALIS - Novembre 2011, IRD, Nouméa, Nouvelle-Calédonie (28 octobre – 13 novembre 2011). Rapport de mission. 2012.

Hocdé R. antérieur à 2012 : 9 publications, 1 collective book, Coordination of the writing, the production and the edition of a collection of 16 thematic booklets. Domains of : data management & information systems, estuarine and coastal environments, decision support tools for stakeholders, integrated coastal zone management (lead author or co-author).

Hocdé R. 2003-2005. 8 posters. Domaines des systèmes d'information, des environnements estuariens et littoraux, des outils d'aide à la décision, de la gestion intégrée des zones côtières. (lead author or co-author)

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INGENIEUR EN INSTRUMENTATION

POSTE Ingénieur d'étude US 191 IMAGO (Depuis 2014). Responsable du laboratoire d'océanographie et géophysique de l'US IMAGO, Centre IRD de Nouméa

FORMATION D.U.T Mesures Physiques, Institut Universitaire de Montpellier

COMPÉTENCES **Electronicien instrumentaliste**

Mise en de toute la partie instrumentation de l'US Imago, notamment lors des campagnes océanographiques

Gestion opérationnelle des réseau d'observation (SNO SSS « Surveillance de la Salinité de Surface », SNO Reeftemps, Réseau des stations sismiques de Nouvelle Calédonie)

Gestion d'équipe

Organisation du travail

Aide à la définition de planning

Suivi des demandes de travaux

Gestion des budgets

Plongée scientifique

Classe 1B plongée hyperbare scientifique

Participation à de nombreuses campagnes en mer

Publications et travaux

- Brissebrat G., Fiat Sylvie, Andriatiana A., Cheype Adrien, Grelet Jacques, Varillon David, Pelletier Bernard, Hocdé Régis, « *Sensor Observation System : optimisation d'un système d'information environnemental dédié capteurs : exemple du SI du réseau d'observation ReefTEMPS* », JRES 2017 : Journées Réseaux de l'Enseignement et de la Recherche, Nantes.
- G.Alory, T.Delcroix, P.Téchiné; D.Diverrès, D.Varillon, S.Cravatte, Y.Gouriou, J.Grelet, S.Jacquin, E.Kestenare, C.Maes, R.Morrow, J.Perrier, G.Reverdin, F.Roubaud : « *The French contribution to the Voluntary Observing Ships network of Sea Surface Salinity* », Deep-Sea Research Part I, Soumission Mars 2015.

- T.Delcroix, MH Radenac, S.Cravatte, G.Alory, L.Gourdeau, F.Léger, A.Singh, D.Varillon : “Sea surface temperature and salinity seasonal changes in the western Solomon and Bismark Seas”, Journal of Geophysical Research , OCEANS, Ref 2013JC009733R, 2014.
- C.Maes, B.Dewitte, J.Sudre, V.Garcon, D.Varillon : “Small-scale features of temperature and salinity surface fields in the Coral Sea”, Journal of Geophysical Research , OCEANS, VOL 118, 1-13, 2013.
- Maes, C.,D. Varillon, A. Ganachaud, F. Gasparin, L. Gourdeau,F.Durand : “Geostrophic component of oceanic jets entering in the eastern Coral Sea as observed with high-resolution XBT surveys (2008-2010)”, Coriolis-Mercator Ocean Quarterly Newsletter/, 41, 25-32, 2011.
- C.Maes, and D. Varillon, “Large-scale climatic and oceanic conditions around Espiritu Santo, Vanuatu archipelago, in *The Natural History of Santo*”, edited by P. Bouchet and B. Richer de Forges, 2011.
- Ioulalalen, M., Y. Wakata, Y. Kawahara, Y. Gouriou and D. Varillon, “Variability of the Sea Surface Salinity (SSS) in the western tropical Pacific: on the ability of an OGCM to simulate the SSS and on the sampling of an operating merchant ship SSS network”. Journal of Oceanography. Vol. 59, No 1, 105-111, 2003.

Encadrement

- 2010 - MAGNEN David – Master 2, Physique et Science pour l’ingénieur, Université Sud Toulon-Var : « Etudes de la variabilité spatio-temporelle de la salinité de surface dans le lagon sud-ouest calédonien à partir d’observations *in situ* ».
- 2007 - GUYADER Thomas – Master 2, Ingénierie informatique, Université de Bretagne Occidentale : « Réalisation d’un portail d’accès WEB pour la consultation de données océanographiques ». Responsable de stage.
- 2005 - HAMARD Antoine – ESEO, Ecole supérieure d’électronique de l’ouest – Elève ingénieur -« Réalisation d’un modèle de base de données océanographiques » - Responsable de stage.
- 1999 – PRUNIER-MIGNOT Marie – ISITV, Institut des Sciences de l’Ingénieur de Toulon et du Var – Elève ingénieur 2^{ème} année – « Users guide for thermosalinograph installation and maintenance aboard a ship. » - Responsable de stage.

Présentations et colloques

- Cheype Adrien, Fiat Sylvie, Pelletier Bernard, Ganachaud Alexandre, Grelet Jacques, Varillon David, Magron F., Hocdé Régis. Système d’information de l’observatoire ReefTEMPS : données de température côtière du Pacifique Sud et Sud-Ouest [poster]. Nouméa : GOPS, 2015, 1 p. JDEV 2015 : Journées Nationales du DEVeloppement Logiciel de l’Enseignement Supérieur et Recherche, Bordeaux.
- D. Varillon, Etat des lieux du monitoring de la salinité de surface à partir de navires marchands au Centre IRD de Nouméa. Réunion technique de l’Observatoire de Recherche pour l’Environnement de la salinité de surface. Centre IRD de Brest, 2005 - 2015
- Delcroix T., D. Dagorne, D. Diverrès, F. Gallois, Y. Gouriou, J. Grelet, J.M. Ihily, S. Jacquin, R. Morrow, G. Reverdin, P. Téchiné, et D. Varillon, L’ORE-SSS : la salinité de surface de la mer pour mieux comprendre le rôle de l’océan sur le climat. Colloque Observatoires de Recherche en Environnement (ORE). Etats des lieux et prospective. Paris, 15-16 novembre 2004. (Présentations orale et poster).
- Delcroix, T., F. Durand, G. Eldin, A. Ganachaud, L. Gourdeau, J. Grelet, C. Maes, et D. Varillon. Contribution au réseau ARGO / CORIOLIS dans le Pacifique tropical ouest : pour mieux comprendre la variabilité ENSO et décennale et en améliorer la prévision. Réunion du groupe mission MERCATOR / CORIOLIS, Toulouse, 6-7 octobre 2004.
- D. Varillon, Etat des lieux du monitoring de la salinité de surface à partir de navires marchands au Centre IRD de Nouméa. Troisième réunion technique de l’Observatoire de Recherche pour l’Environnement de la salinité de surface. Toulouse/LEGOS, 8 octobre 2004.
- D. Varillon, J.M. Ihily, P. Mazoyer, P. Waigna, P. Grimini, T. Delcroix, F. Gallois, A. Ganachaud et A. Hamard. Surveillance thermique et haline de l’océan de surface depuis l’IRD-Nouméa, pour mieux comprendre et prédire la variabilité du climat global et régional. Assises de la Recherche dans le Pacifique Sud, Centre IRD de Nouméa, 23-27 août 2004.
- D. Varillon, Etat des lieux du monitoring de la salinité de surface à partir de navires marchands au Centre IRD de Nouméa. Deuxième réunion technique de l’Observatoire de Recherche pour l’Environnement de la salinité de surface. Centre IRD de Brest, 2002, 2003.
- C.Maes., A. Melet, G. Eldin, J. Lefevre, J. Sudre, and D. Varillon, Flows entering the Solomon Sea: observed features during the FLUSEC-1 cruise in August 2007. AGU Fall meeting, San Francisco, Dec. 10-14, 2007.

- T. Delcroix , D. Diverres , C. Maes, G. Reverdin , P. Téchine, and D. Varillon Monitoring Sea Surface Salinity in the Global Ocean from Ships of Opportunity : the French Observation Service, 1st Joint GOSUD/SAMOS Workshop , Boulder (CO) Mai 2006.
- D.Varillon et D.Diverres, Rapport national sur les lignes de navires marchands, Meeting international Ship Observation Team, 3^{ème} session, Brest, Février 2005.
- Delcroix.T, et D. Varillon, Status of the French IRD contribution to GOSUD, Meeting international Global Ocean Surface Underway Data, 4^{ème} session, Southampton, Septembre 2004.
- Delcroix, T, et D. Varillon, Status of the French IRD contribution to GOSUD, Meeting international Global Ocean Surface Underway Data, 3^{ème} session, Monterey (CA) Novembre 2003.
- D. Varillon, Rapport national sur les lignes de navires marchands, Meeting international « Ship Observation Team », Goa Février 2002, San Diego Mars 2000, Nouméa Octobre 1998.

Campagnes Océanographiques

- Campagne UECOCOT 01, 2018, Chef de mission N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne MALIS 01, 2018, électronicien et plongeur hyperbare, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne PUFFALIS 01, 2017, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, Sondeur ER60, N/O l'Alis
- Campagne COMEVA 02, 2016, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, Sondeur ER60, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne OLZO 01, 2016, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, Sondeur ER60, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne SPOT 01, 02, 03, 04, 06, 07, 08, 10, 11, 12, 2012 - 2016, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, Sondeur ER60, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne NECTALIS 03, 04, 05, 2014 - 2016, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, Sondeur ER60, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne CALLIOPE 02, 03, 2014 - 2016, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, Sondeur ER60, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne SECARGO 01-12, 2008 – 2014, Electronicien embarqué, Déploiement haute densité de sonde de température XBT, M/v Tropical Islander , Pacific Islander.
- Campagne CIRENE 2, Chef de mission, Electronicien embarqué, maintenance des mouillages profond de type « Atlas » dans l'océan Indien, Août 2008, R/v Marion Dufresne.
- Campagne FLUSEC01 – Août 2007, électronique et informatique embarqué, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, mise à l'eau d'un AUV Glider, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne PIRATA16 – EGEE05 – Mai Juin 2007, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, récupération et mise à l'eau de mouillages profonds « PIRATA », N/O ANTEA.
- Campagne SECALIS 01, 02, 03, 04 – 2003 - 2006, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, mise à l'eau d'un AUV Glider. N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne EMERLIS & CoDys, Décembre 2005, électronique et informatique embarqué, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne DIAPALIS 02, 06, 07, 08, 2001 - 2003, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne BOISALIS-02, décembre 2001, électronique et informatique embarquée, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne FRONTALIS-01, mars-avril 2001, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne SABINE 02, 03, 2000 - 2001, électronique et informatique embarquée, N/O l'Alis.
- Campagne WESPALIS-02, avril-mai 2000, électronique et informatique embarquée, acquisition CTD et courantométrie ADCP, N/O l'Alis.

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Curriculum Vitae

Assistante Ingénieur en instrumentation océanographique

Compétences

► Générales

Connaissances

- Océanographie générale
- Physique dans le domaine des technologies et techniques associées à l'instrument
- Technique de mesure et métrologie
- Intégration et organisation d'un ensemble de capteurs de mesure
- Traitement des données scientifiques
- Réglementation d'hygiène et sécurité dans les laboratoires
- Notions de conception
- Gestion de projet
- Travaux en équipe
- Contrôle qualité

Travaux à la mer

- Préparation de missions en mer et mises en œuvre d'instruments océanographiques
- Gestion, maintenance et mise en œuvre de lignes de mouillage instrumentées
Installation, déploiement de sonde CTDs, (capteur de température, conductivité, pression)
- Récolte et conditionnement des échantillons :
 - Échantillonnages : pour l'analyse de l'oxygène, sels nutritifs, alcalinité, pigments
 - Échantillonnages ultra-propres : pour analyse de métaux-traces
- Mise en œuvre des instruments embarqués : Fluorimètre, ADCP de coque, TSGs, sondeur EK 60

Techniques d'analyses chimiques

- Dosage de l'oxygène par la méthode de Winkler
- Dosage de l'alcalinité par dosage potentiométrique
- Dosage de la salinité par un salinomètre Portasal
- Autres manipulations hors contamination

Traitement de données

- Traitement des données par logiciels constructeurs ou développement Matlab ou Perl
- Visualisation de données par ODV (Ocean Data View), Grapher, Surfer
- Développement de programmes Matlab pour le traitement de données physique

► Informatiques

- Systèmes d'exploitation Windows et Linux
- Outils bureautiques Word, Excel, PowerPoint
- Logiciels de visualisation et traitement Matlab, ODV, Seabirds

► Linguistiques

Anglais : Lu, parlé, écrit

Espagnol : Scolaire

Expériences professionnelles

► Sept.2017 - Aujourd'hui

Assistante Ingénieur en instrumentation océanographique à l'Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, IRD, au sein de l'Unité de Service d'Instrumentation, Moyens Analytiques, observatoires en Géophysique et Océanographie, IMAGO :

Nouméa

En charge de :

- Responsable du réseau de navires marchands, (Service National d'Observation de la Salinité de Surface, SNO - SSS), <http://www.legos.obs-mip.fr/observations/sss>
- Campagnes en mer
- Maintenance du réseau côtier, SNO ReefTEMPS, <http://www.reeftemps.science/>
- Maintenance du réseau sismique
- Suivi, gestion et mise en œuvre des instruments océanographiques
- Traitement des données
- Contrôle qualité

- **Fév. 2016 - Sept. 2017** **Assistante Ingénieur en instrumentation océanographique à l'Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, IRD, au sein de l'Unité de Service d'Instrumentation, Moyens Analytiques, observatoires en Géophysique et Océanographie, IMAGO** *Plouzané*
 En charge de :
 - Gestion, suivi, maintenance et mise en œuvre des instruments océanographiques
 - Campagnes en mer
 - Mise en œuvre des mouillages météo-océaniques du SNO PIRATA, (https://www.brest.ird.fr/pirata/pirata_fr.php)
 - Traitement des données
 - Contrôle qualité
- **Jan. 2015 - Jan. 2016** **Ingénieur d'étude en instrumentation océanographique au sein de la Division Technique de l'INSU, dans l'équipe du Parc National des Gliders** *La Seyne sur Mer*
 En charge de : (<http://www.dt.insu.cnrs.fr/spip.php?article8>)
 - Gestion, suivi, maintenance et mise en œuvre des Gliders
 - Traitement des données
 - Contrôle qualité
- **Jan. 2013 - Juillet 2014** **Ingénieur d'étude en instrumentation océanographique au sein de l'institut d'Océanographie de Marseille (MIO)** *La Seyne sur Mer*
 En charge de :
 - Gestion et mise en œuvre des CTDs sur les campagnes HyMeX (Janv. 2013 – mai 2013), ('<http://www.hymex.org>') ainsi que sur le projet TRANSMED, (<http://www.ifremer.fr/transmed/index.php?EX=home>)
 - Traitement et Post-traitement des données
 - Contrôle qualité
 - Participation à l'organisation générale du 7^{ème} workshop International HyMeX - 7-10 October 2013, Cassis, France
 - Campagne en mer MOMARSAT, (aout 2013, juillet 2014), récupération, maintenance et déploiement de la ligne de mouillage instrumentée du LOCEAN, Mise en œuvre des CTDs, rédaction des rapports et fiches de suivies correspondants
- **Déc. 2009 - Déc. 2012** **Ingénieur d'Etude en instrumentation océanographique au sein de la Division Technique de l'INSU** *La Seyne sur Mer*
 En charge de :
 - Gestion et mise en œuvre des calibrations et inter-calibrations des instruments scientifiques fixes à bord des navires de l'INSU
 - Post-traitement des données
 - Recette, tests et configuration des instruments d'une ligne de mouillage inductive prototype, MEUST SE
 - Contrôle qualité des données et métadonnées
 - Campagne en mer TARA OCEAN d'un mois, (mai-juin 2011), mise en œuvre de l'instrumentation océanographique du bord, gestion de l'acquisition des données des capteurs en flux continu et leur maintenance, contrôle qualité
 - Campagne en mer MOMARSAT de 3 semaines, (juillet 2012)
- **Oct. 2008 - Sept. 2009** **Assistante Ingénieur sur le projet EuroSites (European Ocean Observatory Network) au sein du Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche-sur-mer** *Villefranche s/Mer*
 En charge de :
 - Recette, inter-calibration, programmation des capteurs d'une ligne de mouillage
 - Déploiement et maintenance de la ligne
 - Mission mensuelle 'MOOSE – BOUSSOLE', [Mediterranean Ocean Observing System on Environment](#) - BOUée pour l'acquiSition de Séries Optiques à Long termE, mise en œuvre des instruments océanographiques
 - Echantillonnages en mer et dosages en Laboratoire
- **Mars - Juillet 2008** **Stage de fin d'étude : Diffusion de l'eau de pluie dans les couches marines de surface** *Villefranche s/Mer*
 Conception et mise au point d'un prototype de mésocosme in situ fixe/dérivant - Etude de la propagation d'un apport atmosphérique humide dans la couche marine de surface en temps et en profondeur. Simulation de cet apport (traceurs sels nutritifs et strontium), échantillonnage et dosage des traceurs.

Formation scolaire

- ▶ **2007 - 2008** **Master pro en Mesures Instrumentation Surveillance Sol Atmosphère Océan,** *Toulon*
Université des Sciences de Toulon et du Var
- ▶ **2006 - 2007** **Master première année en Sciences de la mer et de l'environnement** *Marseille*
Option physique, Université Aix-Marseille 2, faculté des sciences, Centre d'Océanographie de Marseille, Luminy
- ▶ **2003 – 2004** **Deug Sciences de la Vie, Licence 2 et 3 Sciences de la Mer et de l'Environnement** *Marseille*
Option biologie et écologie, Université Aix-Marseille 2, faculté des sciences, Centre d'Océanographie de Marseille, Luminy
- ▶ **2002 - 2003** **Baccalauréat Scientifique** *Aubagne*
Lycée Joliot-Curie

Centres d'intérêt

Plongée (Niveau 1 – Objectif : Classe 1B), danse (20 ans de classique et autres), musique (8 ans de harpe, guitare), chant, voyages

Curriculum Vitae

Personal Particulars:

Surname: De Ramon N'Yeurt

Given names: Antoine, Alfred

Date of birth: 28 July 1967

Nationality: Fijian

Home Address: P.O. Box 10842, Laucala Beach Estate, Suva, Fiji

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ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9337-150X> | **Scopus:** 6506714135

Ocean Expert: 24180

ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Antoine_De_Ramon_NYeurt

Academic Qualifications:

- **Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Marine Science** (1998). The University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji. Title: The Marine algal flora of Suva Lagoon, Fiji.
- **Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Marine Biology** (1994). The University of the South Pacific, Suva Fiji. Title: The Marine algal flora of Rotuma Island, Fiji.
- **Postgraduate Diploma in Marine Studies** (1991). The University of the South Pacific, Suva Fiji.
- **Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) majors in Physics and Biology** (1989). The University of the South Pacific, Suva Fiji.

Professional Experience:

- **Senior Lecturer**, Pacific Centre for Environment and Sustainable Development (PaCE-SD), the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji (January 2019-present).
- **Lecturer**, Pacific Centre for Environment and Sustainable Development (PaCE-SD), the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji (April 2015-December 2018).
- **Research Fellow**, Pacific Centre for Environment and Sustainable Development (PaCE-SD), the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji (July 2011-March 2015).
- **Deputy Director**, Alliance Française de Suva, Fiji (May 2009-July 2011).
- **Researcher**, French Research Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD), Nouméa, New Caledonia (September 2005-July 2010). Attached to UMR 7138, Tropical Marine Biodiversity Laboratory.
- **Research Associate**, University of California at Berkeley Gump Research Station, Moorea, French Polynesia (October-December 2008). Taxonomy, Moorea Biocode Project.
- **Postdoctoral Researcher**, Marine Ecology Laboratory, University of French Polynesia, Tahiti (July 2000-November 2006). Marine algal flora of French Polynesia.
- **Research Fellow**, Marine Studies Program, the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji (1998-2000). Curator of marine algal collections.
- **Research Associate**, Marine Ecology Laboratory, University of French Polynesia, Tahiti (1995-1997). Marine algal flora of French Polynesia; setting up of the algal Herbarium (UPF).
- **Research Fellow**, Marine Studies Program, The University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji (1994-1995). Curator of marine algal collections.
- **Graduate Research Assistant**. Marine Studies Program, the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji (1994). Phycology Laboratory.

Research Attachments:

- **Department of Botany, Te Papa Tongarewa Museum of New Zealand (WELT), Wellington** (13th of March to 2nd of April 2008). Taxonomic identification of algal collections from Fiji and the Cook Islands.
- **Natural History Museum (BM), London, United Kingdom** (18th April to 18th May 2005). Re-evaluation of the holdings of marine algae from the Southern Pacific.
- **Algal Ecophysiology and Biotechnology Laboratory (LEBHAM), Technopôle Brest, France** (1st June to 31st July 2001). Revision of the red marine algal flora of the Rade of Brest.
- **Division of Biological Sciences, Hokkaido University, Sapporo, Japan** (June 11 to July 8, 1999). Classical and Molecular taxonomy of tropical marine algae.

Consultancies / Expertise:

- **Tuvalu Reef-to-Ridge (R2R) Project** (October 2017-February 2019). Research on coastal water quality monitoring and algal bloom issues in Tuvalu. Marine biodiversity surveys; conducting community trainings in the sustainable management of coastal water resources.
- **Korean Research Institute of Ships and Ocean engineering (KRISO), Kiribati** (18-25 July 2016). Sustainable Seawater Utilization Academy, Kiribati. Delivering lectures on “Cultivation of marine plants for bioenergy using Ocean Thermal Conversion (OTEC) waste water”.
- **TOTAL (Fiji) Ltd.** (19-26 September 2014). Installation of a rural solar lighting project for four households on the remote island of Rotuma, Fiji.
- **Institute of Applied Sciences (IAS), The University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji** (August 14th to 16th 2012). Development and delivery of a workshop on the identification of tropical marine algae.
- **French Coral Reef Institute (IFRECOR), Bora Bora, French Polynesia** (2002). Setting up of a coral reef monitoring program in response to coral bleaching and mortality.
- **World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF), Rarotonga, Cook Islands** (1999). Illustrated field guide to the common marine algae of the Cook Islands.
- **United Nations Development Program, Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO / UNDP), Fiji** (1997). South Pacific Aquaculture Project Phase II. Culture trials for seaweeds (*Meristotheca* sp.) in Rotuma Island.
- **French Overseas Territories Research Institute (ORSTOM), Tahiti, French Polynesia** (1995). TYPATOLL Project. Underwater sampling and taxonomic analysis of algae of Tuamotu Archipelago and Moorea Island.

Professional Development:

- **Training on deriving records of long-term changes in ocean acidification from coral cores, and linking to modern seawater pH measurements** (2019). National Oceanography Centre (NOC), University of Southampton and Cardiff University, United Kingdom.
- **Technical Course on the Management, Analysis and Quality Control of Ocean Acidification Observation Data** (2018). International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) Environment Laboratories, Monaco.
- **Advanced Training Course on Ocean Acidification Monitoring** (2018). University of Hawai'i at Manoa / the Ocean Foundation, USA.
- **Applied Training Course on Ocean Acidification** (2017). The University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji / the Ocean Foundation, USA.
- **Practical Training Course on Ocean Acidification** (2017). The University of the South

Pacific, Suva, Fiji / the Ocean Foundation, USA.

- **Satellite Remote Sensing Summer School** (2017). Cornell University and the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji.
- **First-Aid Training Course Certification** (2017). Fiji Red Cross and the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji.
- **Ocean Acidification Best Practice and SeaFET Training Workshop** (September 8th to 11th, 2015). Auckland University, New Zealand.
- **Certification in Biomedical Responsible Conduct of Research** (2014). Office of Research Education, The University of Kansas, USA.
- **Online Facilitation Course** (2013). Open Polytechnic, New Zealand and the University of the South Pacific Center for Flexible Learning, Suva, Fiji.
- **Coralline Algae Taxonomy and Microscopic Histological Techniques Workshop** (September 3-7, 2012). Department of Biodiversity and Conservation Biology, Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of the Western Cape, South Africa.
- **NCAR Command Language (NCL) Workshop** (13th to 16th March 2012). National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) of the University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (UCAR), Boulder, Colorado, USA,
- **Development of Postgraduate courses using Moodle** (16th-17th February 2012). The University of the South Pacific Centre for Flexible Learning, Suva, Fiji.
- **MATLAB statistical package expert training workshop** (28th November 2011). ICT Engineering Computer Lab, the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji.
- **Qualification aux fonctions de Maître de Conférences** (2010). Ability to teach at university level in the French academic system. Section 68, Biology of Organisms.. National Council of Universities, Paris. Nr. 10268117760.
- **Training Course in Molecular Biology Techniques for Marine Algae** (18 May to 18 July 1998, 1st September to 26th October, 1998). Marine Biotechnology Institute (MBI), Shimizu, Japan.
- **Open Water SCUBA Diving certification** (1995). PADI, Brisbane, Australia.
- **Practical Taxonomy and Identification of Crustose Coralline Algae** (3-7 October 1994). International Ocean Institute / The University of the South Pacific Marine Studies Program, Suva, Fiji / University of the Western Cape, South Africa.
- **Workshop on Primary Production** (October 6-10, 1992). ORSTOM French Polynesia / The University of the South Pacific Marine Studies Program, Suva, Fiji.
- **Radio Amateur Certification** (1987). City and Guilds of London Institute, United Kingdom. Includes knowledge of Morse Code at 35 words per minute.

Administrative Experience:

- **Member of six Human Resources Selection and Appointment Committees** for staff positions at the University of the South Pacific in Fiji (2013-2018). Involved in the screening of candidates, the interview process and the final selection process.
- **Drafting of a revised Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)** for collaboration between the University of the South Pacific and the French Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, IRD (2016).
- **Attendance at University Senate Meetings** on behalf of the PaCE-SD Director, as required on request.
- Member of the PaCE-SD **Research Committee**
- Member of the PaCE-SD **Academic Committee**
- Representative of PaCE-SD at the **University Scholarship Committee**.
- Founder and leader of the PaCE-SD **Energy Usage Efficiency Committee** towards reducing the Carbon Footprint of the Centre.

- **Lead Judge, 3rd Faculty of Business and Economics Debate, 4th Annual Debate Series**, the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji, May 2nd. Debate between the School of Management and Public Administration and the School of Tourism and Hospitality Management on the topic “Sea-bed mining is essential for PICs’ prosperity”.
- **Organisation of a scientific workshop on climate change** between the French Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD) and the University of the South Pacific staff and students (27-29 August, 2013). The workshop was attended by seven invited expert researchers from IRD New Caledonia, some 20 postgraduate students from USP (FSTE, PaCE-SD, Pacific Studies) and many USP staff.
- **Draft Consultative USP Strategic Plan 2013-2018 meetings** with the Vice-Chancellor, senior administrative team and heads of schools (August and September, 2012). Drafting and editing of the strategic theme “Environment, Sustainable Development and Climate Change Adaptation” for the Strategic Plan document.
- **Deputy Director, Alliance Française de Suva, Fiji** (2009-2011). Administrative duties for the daily running of the centre.

Publications:

Books (3)

- Paeniu L., Iese V., Jacot Des Combes H., **De Ramon N’Yeurt A.**, Korovulavula I., Koroi A., Sharma P., Hobgood N., Chung K. & Devi A. (2015). *Coastal Protection: Best Practices from the Pacific*. Pacific Centre for Environment and Sustainable Development (PaCE-SD), the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji, 98 pp. ISBN 978-982-01-0936-0.
- Payri, C. E., **N’Yeurt, A.D.R.** & Orempuller, J. (2000). *Algues de Polynésie Française / Algae of French Polynesia*. Bilingual (English / French) illustrated guide. Editions au Vent des Iles, Papeete. 380 p., 250 colour photographs. ISBN 2-909790-82-7.
- N’Yeurt, A.D.R.**, McClatchey, W.C. & Schmidt, H. (1996). *A Bibliography of Rotuma*. Pacific Information Centre / The University of the South Pacific Marine Studies Program Technical Report Series 1996(2), Suva. xiii + 131 p. ISBN 982-01-0292-8.

Book Chapters (4)

- Brodie, G. and **N’Yeurt, A.D.R.** (2018) Impacts of Climate Change on Seagrasses and Seagrass Habitats Relevant to the Pacific Islands. *Pacific Marine Climate Change Report Card: Science Review 2018*, pp 112-131.
- Carlson B., Lovell E., **N’Yeurt A.D.R.** and Sykes, H. (2018). Republic of Fiji. *In: Moritz C, Vii J, Lee Long W, Tamelander J, Thomassin A, and Planes S (Eds), Status and Trends of Coral Reefs of the Pacific*. Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network, pp. 131-135.
- N’Yeurt, A.D.R.** & Iese, V. (2015). Marine plants as a sustainable source of agrifertilizers for Small Island Developing States (SIDS). *In: Wayne G. Ganpat & Wendy-Ann Isaac, Eds, Impacts of Climate Change on Food Security in Small Island Developing States*. IGI Global, Hershey, Pennsylvania, pp. 280-311 (ISBN: 978-1-4666-6501-9).
- Havea P.H., Tamani A.T., Siga A., **N’Yeurt, A.D.R.**, Jacot Des Combes H., Hemstock S.L. & Luetz J.M. (2020). Resilience in Education: An Example from Fiji and TVET. *In Leal Filho, W. (Ed) Managing Climate Change Adaptation in the Pacific Region*. Springer International Publishing, Cham.

Journal Articles (36)

- Dumas P., Fiat S., Durbano A., Peignon C., Moutham G., Ham J., Gereva S., Kaku R., Chateau O., Wantiez L., **De Ramon N'Yeurt A.**, Adjeroud M. 2020. Citizen Science, a promising tool for detecting and monitoring outbreaks of the crown-of-thorns starfish *Acanthaster* spp. *Scientific Reports* 10: 291. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-57251-8>.
- Havea P.H., **N'Yeurt, A.D.R.**, Jacot Des Combes H., Hemstock S.L., Luetz J.M., Liava'a L. F. C. & Havea E. (2020). Tā e Lango' kei Mama'o: A Framework for Resilience Development in Tonga. Lancet, London, UK.
- Lal, R., **N'Yeurt, A.D.R.**, Riley, R.H., Kininmonth, S. and Rico, C. (2018). The effects of a stressed inshore urban reef on coral recruitment in Suva harbour, Fiji. *Ecology and Evolution* (Wiley Open Access, Accepted. DOI: 10.1002/ece3.4641).
- Chandra, V.V., Hemstock, S.L., Mwabonje, O.N., **N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** and Woods, J. (2018) Life cycle assessment of sugarcane growing process in Fiji. *Sugar Tech* 2018: 1-8. Print ISSN 0972-1525. Online ISSN 0974-0740. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12355-018-0607-1>.
- Chandra V.V., Hemstock S.L., **N'Yeurt A.D.R.** and Surroop, D. (2017). Environmental and economic study for a prospective ethanol industry in Fiji. *Progress in Industrial Ecology – An International Journal* 11: 146-162.
- Payri C.E., **N'Yeurt A.D.R.**, Fiat S. & Andréfouët, S. (2016). La macroflore marine de l'archipel des Marquises / The macroalgal flora of the Marquesas Islands. In Galzin R., Duron S.-D. & Meyer J.-Y. (eds), *Biodiversité terrestre et marine des îles Marquises, Polynésie française*. Société française d'Ichtyologie, Paris: pp. 207-219.
- Shipley, G.P., Taylor, D.A., **N'Yeurt, A.D.R.**, Tyagi, A., Tiwari, G. & Redd, A. (2016). Genetic Evidence for Modifying Oceanic Boundaries Relative to Fiji. *Human Biology*, Summer 2016, v. 88, no. 3, pp. 232–244. doi: 10.13110/humanbiology.88.3.0232.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** and Iese, V. (2015). *Erratum* to: The proliferating brown alga *Sargassum polycystum* in Tuvalu, South Pacific: assessment of the bloom and applications to local agriculture and sustainable energy. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 27(5): 2047 (DOI 10.1007/s10811-015-0528-2).
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** and Iese, V. (2015). The invasive brown alga *Sargassum polycystum* in Tuvalu, South Pacific: Assessment of the bloom and applications to local agriculture and sustainable energy. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 27(5): 2037-2045 (DOI: 10.1007/s10811-014-0435-y).
- N'Yeurt, A. D. R.** & Tsuda, R.T. (2014). New records of marine algae from Tonga, Central Polynesia. *Marine Biodiversity Records* 7: 1-8 (e111).
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.**, Chynoweth, D.P., Capron, M.E., Stewart, J.R., Hasan, M.A. (2012). Negative Carbon via Ocean Afforestation. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection* 90: 467-474.
- Payri, C.E., **N'Yeurt, A. D. R.** & Mattio, L. (2011). Benthic algal and seagrass communities in Baa Atoll, Maldives. *Atoll Research Bulletin* 590: 31-66.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** & Payri, C.E. (2010). Marine benthic algal flora of French Polynesia. III. Rhodophyta, with additions to the Chlorophyta and Phaeophyceae. *Cryptogamie, Algologie* 31: 1-205.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** & Payri, C.E. (2009). Four new species of Rhodophyceae from Fiji, French Polynesia and Vanuatu, South Pacific. *Phycological Research* 57: 12-24.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** & Payri, C.E. (2008). *Sebdenia cerebriformis* sp. nov. (Sebdeniaceae, Halymeniales) from the southwestern Pacific Ocean. *Phycological Research* 56: 13-20.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** & Payri, C.E. (2007). *Grammephora peyssonnelioides* gen. et sp. nov. (Rhodophyta, Rhodymeniaceae) from the Solomon Islands, South Pacific. *Phycological Research* 55: 286-294.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** & Payri, C.E. (2007). Marine benthic algal flora of French Polynesia. II. Chlorophyta. *Cryptogamie, Algologie* 28: 3-88.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.**, Wynne, M.J., & Payri, C.E. (2007). *Myriogramme melanesiensis* and *M. heterostroma* (Delesseriaceae, Rhodophyta), two new species from the Solomon Islands and Vanuatu. *Contributions of the University of Michigan Herbarium* 25: 213-224.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** & Payri, C.E. (2006). Marine benthic algal flora of French Polynesia. I. Phaeophyceae. *Cryptogamie, Algologie* 27: 111-152.

- Indy, J. R., N'Yeurt, A.D.R. & Yasui, H. (2006). Reproductive morphology and taxonomic reappraisal of *Exophyllum wentii* Weber-van Bosse (Rhodomelaceae, Rhodophyta). *Phycological Research* 54: 308-316.
- Lobban, C.S. & N'Yeurt, A.D.R. (2006). Provisional keys to the genera of seaweeds of Micronesia, with new records for Guam and Yap. *Micronesica* 39: 73-105.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R., Payri, C.E., Gabrielson, P.W. & S. Fredericq, S. (2006). *Pinnatiphycus menouana* gen. et sp. nov. (Rhodophyta: Dicranemataceae) from New Caledonia and Fiji (South Pacific): vegetative and reproductive morphology and molecular phylogeny. *Phycologia* 45: 422-431.
- Verbruggen, H., De Clerck, O., N'Yeurt, A.D.R., Spalding, H. & Vroom, P.S. (2006). Phylogeny and taxonomy of *Halimeda incrassata*, including descriptions of *H. kanaloana* and *H. heteromorpha* spp. nov. (Bryopsidales, Chlorophyta). *European Journal of Phycology* 41: 337-362.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R. & Payri, C.E. (2004). A preliminary annotated checklist of the marine algae and seagrasses of the Wallis Islands (French Overseas Territory of Wallis and Futuna), South Pacific. *Australian Systematic Botany* 17: 367-397.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R. (2002). A revision of *Amansia glomerata* C. Agardh, *Amansia rhodantha* (Harvey) J. Agardh and *Melanamansia glomerata* (C. Agardh) R. E. Norris (Rhodophyta: Rhodomelaceae). *Botanica Marina* 45: 231-242.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R. (2001). Marine algae from the Suva Reef, Fiji. *Australian Systematic Botany* 14: 689-869.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R. & South, G.R. (1997). Biodiversity and biogeography of marine benthic algae in the Southwest Pacific, with special reference to Rotuma and Fiji. *Pacific Science* 51: 18-28.
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Conference Proceedings (2)

- Capron, M.E., Blaylock, B., Lucas, K., Chambers, M.D., Stewart, J.R., DiMarco, S. F., Whilden, K., Wang, B., Kim, M.H., N'Yeurt, A.D.R., Webb, C., Moscicki, Z., Sullivan, C., Tsukrov, I., Swift, M.R., James, S.C., Brooks, M., Howden, S., Fredericq, S., Krueger-Hadfield, S.A., Piper, D. (2018). Ocean Forests: Breakthrough Yields for Macroalgae. *Proceedings of the OCEANS 2018 Charleston Conference*, October 22-25, 2018. Charleston, South Carolina, USA. 6 pp.
- Charan, H., N'Yeurt, A.D.R., Iese, V. and Chopin, T. (2017). The effect of temperature on the growth of two pest seaweeds in Fiji. *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Energy, Environment and Climate*: 336-341.
- Wandres M., Aucan J., Jackson N., N'Yeurt A.D.R. and Damlamian, H. (2019). Distant-source swell events cause coastal inundation on Fiji's Coral Coast. *Proceedings of the Second International*

Workshop on Waves, Storm Surges and Coastal Hazards (submitted).

Professional or Technical Reports (8)

- Iese, V. and **De Ramon N'Yeurt, A.** (2018). *Final Report for Seaweed Monitoring Survey in Tuvalu*. Tuvalu Reef to Ridge Programme and United Nations Development Programme, Funafuti. 85pp.
- Iese, V. and **De Ramon N'Yeurt, A.** (2018). *Lipoti Mo Te Iloiloga O Savea Ki Limu I Tuvalu*. Tuvalu Reef to Ridge Programme and United Nations Development Programme, Funafuti. 85pp. In Tuvaluan.
- Iese, V., **De Ramon N'Yeurt, A.** and Vanoh, R. (2018). *Data Analysis and Vetiver Planting Training Report*. Tuvalu Reef to Ridge Programme and United Nations Development Programme, Funafuti. 56pp.
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- Payri, C.E., Pichon, M., Benzoni, F., **N'Yeurt, A.D.R.**, Verbruggen, H. & Andréfouët, S. (2002). 'Atelier Marin Wallis 2002. Contribution a l'Etude de la Biodiversité dans les Récifs Coralliens de Wallis. Scleractiniaires et Macrophytes'. Université de la Polynésie française: Outumaoro, 54 p., 6 plates with colour photographs, Landsat map.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** (1999). *A Preliminary Illustrated Field Guide to the Common Marine Algae of the Cook Islands (Rarotonga and Aitutaki)*. World Wide Fund for Nature, Rarotonga. 74 p.
- Payri, C.E.; Orepuller, J. & **N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** (1995). *TYPATOLL. Les peuplements de macrophytes. Rapport préliminaire, décembre 1995*. Université Française du Pacifique / ORSTOM, Papeete, Tahiti. 5 pp.
- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** (1993). *A Preliminary Checklist of the Marine Benthic Algae of Rotuma*. University of the South Pacific Marine Studies Programme Technical Report Nr. 93/2. 14 pp.

Datasets (1)

- Varillon David, Fiat Sylvie, Magron Franck, Allenbach Michel, Hoibian Thierry, **De Ramon N'Yeurt Antoine**, Ganachaud Alexandre, Aucan Jérôme, Pelletier Bernard, Hocdé Régis (2018). ReefTEMPS : the observation network of the coastal sea waters of the South, West and South-West Pacific. SEANOE. <http://doi.org/10.17882/55128>.

Magazine Articles (1)

- N'Yeurt, A.D.R.** (2017). Working 6m from Rotuma the 'Island Brew' Way. *Practical Wireless* March 2017: 58-60.

Research Projects:

External Projects and Generated Income, 2012-2018 (Euros)

Duration	Title of Project	Project Income	Donors
2012-2014	ReefTEMPS Fiji: Processing and monitoring of climate-change data for coral reefs of the Fiji Islands	6 350,00 €	Embassy of France in Fiji; Fonds Pacifique
2014-2016	VerTEMP: Expanding in range and vertical depth the Network of Precise Temperature Measurement in Fijian Coral Reefs (VerTemp Project).	10 000,00 €	Embassy of France in Fiji; Fonds Pacifique
2015-2016	VABIOMAR: Valorization of proliferating marine biomass (seaweeds, crown-of-thorn starfish) to improve energy and food security of isolated Pacific communities	17 020,00 €	Government of New Caledonia
2015-2017	OREANET: Oceania REgional Acanthaster NETwork	4 000,00 €	Embassy of France in Vanuatu; Fonds Pacifique
2016-2018	COPRA: Climate and Oceanography in the Pacific: Risks and Adaptation	43 125,00 €	Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD), New Caledonia
	TOTAL	80 495,00 €	

Surface Seawater Temperature (SST)

2012-2018 Project Leader for the University of the South Pacific's ReefTemps programme in collaboration with the French Research Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD) and the Pacific Community (SPC) in obtaining precise continuous data on coastal seawater temperatures and other oceanographic parameters around the Fiji Islands using a network of precise temperature data loggers (12 sites to date). Responsible for the selection of sites, logistics of deployment, logger acquisition, setup and maintenance, as well as data retrieval and uploading to data portals.

Deepwater Oceanic Temperature and Wave Buoy

2018 Initiation and deployment of a deepwater mooring observation platform and surface wave buoy at an offshore site in Fiji in collaboration with the Pacific Community (SPC), the Fiji Meteorological Service, the Fiji Navy and the French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD). The mooring is a combination of a surface wave buoy (provided by SPC), which is a key component of the Coastal Inundation Forecasting Demonstration Project in Fiji (CIFDP), and a subsurface 200m long cable and array of temperature and pressure sensors provided by USP and IRD, which is a component of the Coastal Oceanography in the Pacific, Risk and Adaptation project (COPRA) in collaboration with IRD.

Ocean Acidification

2018 Initiation and deployment of a coastal Ocean Acidification (pH) monitoring program around Fiji. First monitoring station deployed in March 2018 off the Suva Reef at -12m, to monitor climate change signals and providing real-time OA data via satellite

telemetry. Sensors and equipment in collaboration with the National Oceanography Centre of the UK (NOC) and the GOA-ON Network (SEAFETs). Participation in a number of OA-related advanced training workshops and conferences.

Conferences:

- 2018 (12th October). **Oral presentation at the Blue-Green Economy Symposium** organised by the Korea Institute of Ocean Science and Technology (Korea Research Institute of Ships and Ocean Engineering). Sofitel Spa and Resort, Nadi, Fiji. Title of presentation: “**Cultivation of seaweed by use of discharged deep seawater from Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC) plant**”.
- 2017 (23th to 24th August). Oral presentation at the **First High Level Pacific Blue Economy Conference, Grand Pacific Hotel, Suva, Fiji**. Convened by the Pacific Island Development Forum (PIDF), this high-level conference brought together leaders and representatives from national governments, the scientific community, academic and educational institutions, the private sector and civil society organisations on building on the outcomes of the June 2017 UN Oceans Conference and towards achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 14 and on existing Pacific commitments and frameworks, by holding open and frank discussions to define the Blue Economy from a Pacific perspective along with measures necessary to achieve a sustainable Blue Economy. Title of presentation: **Ocean Algal Afforestation (OAA): Prospects for the Pacific and Global Implications**.
- 2017 (January 19th-20th). Presented orally at the **International Conference on the Impacts of Ocean Acidification on Marine Ecosystems and Necessary Policy Measures**. The Ocean Policy Research Institute, Sasakawa Peace Foundation, Tokyo, Japan. Title of presentation: “Coastal Temperature and Ocean Acidification Monitoring Strategy for the USP Region – Present Status and Future Plans.” Member of the Discussion Panel for Session 3: Towards Networking in the West Pacific Region”.
- 2016 (29 July) Participation at the **New Zealand Pacific Partnership on Ocean Acidification (PPOA) Fiji project Inception Workshop** in Suva, Fiji. Organised by the South Pacific Regional Environment Program (SPREP).
- 2016 (19-24 June). Presented at the **22nd International Seaweed Symposium held in Copenhagen, Denmark**. Title of presentation: **Sustainable Fertilisers & Biofuels from Overabundant Seaweeds for Pacific Islands**.
- 2016 (May 8th-10th). Presentation at the **Third GOA-ON Science Workshop, CSIRO Marine Laboratories, Hobart, Tasmania, Australia**. Organised by the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), the International Atomic Energy Agency (IEA) and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) of the USA. Title of presentation: **Monitoring Platforms for Ocean Acidification and Temperature in the Fiji Islands**.
- 2015 (16th to 19th November). Oral presentation on my behalf at the **Pacific Islands GIS/RS User Conference** held in Suva, Fiji. Title: Martias, C., Dupouy, C., Singh, A., N’Yeurt, A., Lal, S., Douillet, P., Drouzy, M., Wattelez, G. and Lefevre, J. *Dynamics of CDOM in the South Pacific: An application of ocean colour remote sensing*.
- 2015 (October 7th to 9th). Oral Presentation at the **Pacific Islands Regional Ocean**

Acidification Workshop, Stamford Plaza, Auckland, New Zealand. Organised by the South Pacific Regional Environment Program (SPREP) and the Global Ocean Acidification Observation Network (GOA-ON). Title of presentation: "**Coastal Temperature and Ocean Acidification Monitoring Strategy for the USP Region: Present Status and Future Plans**".

- 2015 (May 4th to 7th). Presented at the **First Pacific Islands Training Workshop on Ocean Observations and Data Applications (PI-1)** organized by the World Meteorological Organisation/IOC Data Buoy Cooperation Panel (DBCP) and Partners, Koror State Government Office Assembly Hall, Republic of Palau.
- 2014 (September 15th-17th). Presentation at the **2014 Asia Pacific Resilience Innovation Summit and Expo (APRISE2014), Honolulu Convention Center, Hawaii, USA.** Finalist in the Islands Innovation and Pacific Agriculture Innovation Challenge 2014. Oral presentation: **Pathways to Island Energy and Food Independence** (Sarah Hemstock, Antoine D.R. Ramon N'Yeurt, Viliamu Iese, Mark E. Capron, Jim Stewart, Frank Sudia, Mohammed Hasan). Poster: **Seaweed-Biogas Pathways to Island Energy and Food Independence** (Antoine D.R. N'Yeurt, Sarah Hemstock, Jim R. Stewart & Mark E. Capron).
- 2014 (August 18th to 21st). Participated and contributed towards a **Regional Plan for Marine Protected Areas, Nouméa, New Caledonia.** Attended the French Agency for Marine Protected Areas - PACIOCEA (Pacific Ocean Ecosystem Analysis) Technical Workshop. Purpose: Analyze the current situation and Design future scenarios for the Pacific Region. Facilitated the distribution of a PACIOCEA questionnaire to USP students about their perception of priorities in Marine Conservation issues.
- 2014 (July 14th to 18th). Presented two oral papers at the **Second International Conference on Climate Change and Renewable Energy (ICRECC) at the University of the South Pacific, Suva, Fiji,** Paper titles: (1) Pacific Community Development through Biofuel Generation from Marine Biomass. (2) Small Island Community Ownership of Rural Electrification using Solar Energy – Rotuma Island Case Study. Both papers were successfully presented with interest shown from the public.
- 2014 (June 21st to 28th). Presented an oral paper at the **5th Congress of the International Society for Applied Phycology (ISAP 2014) in Sydney, Australia.** Paper entitled: Pacific Community Development Through Fertilizer Production and Biofuel Generation from the Seaweeds *Gracilaria edulis* and *Sargassum polycystum* (Authors A.D.R. N'Yeurt, S.L. Hemstock, V. Iese). Paper was successfully presented on Wednesday 25th of June.
- 2014 (February 24th to 28th). **American Geophysical Union (AGU) Ocean Sciences Meeting, Honolulu, Hawaii, USA.** This is a two-yearly meeting bringing together eminent ocean scientists from all over the world, with 4,500 participants and over 3,500 posters at the 2014 session. Presentation on "**Restoring ocean health and primary productivity with managed seaweed forests: a mass balance of carbon and nutrient cycles**" and two posters "**Pacific community development through fertilizer production and biofuel generation from marine biomass**" and "**Moving ocean policy from "take" to "give and take" with managed ocean seaweed forests**".
- 2012 (July 9th to 13th). Attending the **12th International Coral Reef Symposium (ICRS-12)**

in Cairns, Australia. This is a major 4-yearly event bringing together worldwide leading experts on coral reef research, including on aspects of climate change and coral reefs.

- 2012 (April 23rd to 27th). Attending the **10th International Conference on Southern Hemisphere Meteorology and Oceanography (ICSHMO 10) in Nouméa, New Caledonia.** This conference was run under the auspices of the American Meteorological Society (AMS), in collaboration with the Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD, the French Overseas Research Institute) and Météo-France (the French Meteorological Services unit).
- 2005 Communication to the **Fourth Asian Pacific Phycological Forum, Bangkok, Thailand, 30 October to 4 November, 2005** by Claude E. PAYRI and Antoine de R. N'Yeurt: Could global warming affect the marine algal flora of French Polynesia and other south Pacific Islands?
- 2005 Presentation to the « **Colloque sur la Biodiversité des îles Australes** » (**Biodiversity of the Austral Islands**) (**Institut Louis Malardé, Papeete, Tahiti, French Polynesia, 08-10 novembre 2005**). Topic: (Claude PAYRI & Antoine N'YEURT) : Could global warming affect the marine algal flora of Rapa Island ?
- 1994 **Fifth International Phycological Congress, Qingdao, P. R. China 25 June - 2 July, 1994.**

Memberships to Associations:

- French Association of Scientific Divers (COLIMPHA) Nr 777
- International Phycological Society (IPS)
- Fiji Association of Radio Amateurs (FARA), Suva since 1988
- National Geographic Society (NGS), Washington. Since January 1, 1987.

Awards:

- The University of the South Pacific, 1998. **Gold Medal for best thesis in Science.**
- The University of the South Pacific Research Office, 25 November 2013: \$660 FJD For the journal publication “**Negative carbon via Ocean Afforestation**” (**B-ranked**)
- The University of the South Pacific Research Office, 13 November 2015: \$402 FJD For the Book Chapter “**Marine plants as a sustainable source of agrifertilizers for Small Island Developing States (SIDS)**” (**B-ranked**)
- The University of the South Pacific Research Office, 12 September 2017: \$240 FJD for the Book Chapter “**The Marine Macroalgal Flora of the Marquesas**” (**B-ranked**)
- The University of the South Pacific Research Office, 16 October 2018: \$1,200 FJD for the journal article “**Environmental and economic study for a prospective ethanol industry in Fiji**” (**A-ranked**)

Peer-Review for Scientific Journals:

Phycologia

1. *Phycological Research*
2. *Cryptogamie, Algologie*

3. *Botanica Marina*
4. *Journal of Applied Phycology*
5. *Atoll Research Bulletin*
6. *Journal of Ecotoxicology*
7. *South Pacific Journal of Natural Science*
8. *South African Journal of Botany*
9. *Pacific Science*
10. *Micronesica*
11. *African Journal of Botany*
12. *Chinese Journal of Oceanology & Limnology*
13. *Journal des Océanistes* (on Editorial Board for the Coordination of an entire issue on climate change, 2018-2019)
14. Expert Reviewer for the *Second Order Draft of the IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate* (SROCC), November 2018-January 2019.

Languages:

English (oral, written, fluent)

French (oral, written, fluent)

Spanish (written, fair)

Russian (written, fair)

Latin (written, scientific)

Rotuman (oral, fluent).

Technical Skills:

- High level of **IT-related knowledge**, advice given (including to IT officers of PaCE-SD) on ways to remove viruses and install software on computers, as well as many other computer-related issues. Data recovery and servicing of external hard drive for postgraduate students who had lost their climate data files; advice on purchase of quality IT equipment.
- Ability to **diagnose and service electronic hardware** and faults in computers and other equipment. Qualified Amateur-Radio operator, with a broad knowledge in **electronics and communications**.
- **Scientific / Oceanographic Instrumentation skills** (loggers, CTDs, Ocean Acidification sensors, Water Quality meters, etc.) used in climate change projects and scientific research. Ability to design, seek contractors for and implement the installation of robust field housings for **climate change data monitoring platforms**.
- **Travel advice for postgraduate students and staff** (extensive knowledge of travel in Europe, North America, Australia, New Zealand, Asia (Japan and China), and South Pacific countries, including Hawaii and French territories).
- **Scientific SCUBA diving skills** (licensed since 1995 with over **80 scientific dives** up to 35m depth logged across the Pacific, member of PADI and COLIMPHA Scientific Diving community). Regular SCUBA diving to install, rotate and maintain scientific climate monitoring platforms.
- **Botanical and Taxonomic skills** (marine botany) with a proven track record of publishing new records, species and genera of marine algae in the Pacific region, and floristic / biodiversity studies for renowned research institutions (French Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD), University of French Polynesia, Bishop Museum of Hawaii, University of California at Berkeley, WWF-Pacific, NIWA New Zealand, etc.). Identification of marine algae on a voluntary basis for the IAS marine natural products project.
- **Organisation of Workshops:** Responsible for the organisation, funding and logistics of a one-day workshop for a community in **Viseisei Village, Fiji** on the topic of using **seaweed**

fertiliser on agricultural crops. Organised by PaCE-SD, USP in collaboration with Organic Matters Foundation of Australia. April 9th, 2014.

Referees:

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